

IN THE NAME OF GODMENT

(Identity impression)

Arguments denying and violating the evidence of religion in establishing salvation based on objective evidence in Hume's perspective

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Abstract:

Asking God is one of the most important and central issues of philosophical and theological systems. By choosing Hume and Leibniz from two philosophical systems, empiricist and rationalist, this article examines and compares their opinions about God. It can be said that Hume and Leibniz have a serious conflict in this matter, because Hume, based on his empiricist system, objects and criticizes the same arguments that Leibniz uses to prove the existence of God. Leibniz's philosophy is a God-centered philosophy, while in Hume's philosophical system, where human knowledge is rooted in sense and experience, there is no place left for belief in God, which is a meta-experiential issue. In the two philosophers' view of God's place in the discussion of causality, we can see a clear contrast. As an example, Hume seriously criticizes the same arguments that Leibniz expresses in proving the existence of God. Some believe that Hume hid himself behind a few fictional characters named Demi (representative of rationalists) and Clindis and Philo (representative of empiricists) in "Dialogues on Natural Religion" and this has led to different interpretations of his view of God; But what is certain is that Hume is a full-fledged empiricist, and he probably agrees with Philo and Klindis in this treatise. In this work, as well as in the eleventh chapter of the research book, he criticized the three proofs of God's existence (order proof, cosmological proof and existential proof). It is not objective but only subjective, it leaves no way to prove the existence of God and to believe in his existence. Because the proofs to prove the existence of God are not out of two situations: either they are lemmas in which the existence of the cause leads to the existence of the effect, or they are those in which the existence of the effect leads to the existence of the cause and prove it, but Hume, considering that causal necessity And it denies maaluli, it can neither accept lemma proofs (such as existential proofs) nor the proofs of order or cosmology, which are one of the proofs. On the other hand, Leibniz's philosophy should be considered a philosophy based on the centrality of God. In the discussion of causality, Leibniz considers the cause to be unique in the subject and the end, and God is the source of issuing both. Therefore, in Leibniz's view, all types and manifestations of causality are caused by the transcendental essence.

Introduction:

One of the most common interpretations of the reason for order in proving the existence of God is the interpretation based on parables. A speech that has been the focus of David Hume's scathing criticism. But since Hume's serious criticisms on the reason for order, many theistic thinkers in different religious traditions have tried to give a suitable and convincing answer to Hume's criticisms. As Hume believed, reasoning through order cannot be considered as a successful philosophical argument in terms of natural theology; Because it is

not able to prove the desired God of religious people in different religious traditions, because it confirms only a part of the elements of theism and is completely ambiguous in relation to other parts; In the end, Professor Motahari also believes that such proof alone cannot prove the God desired by religious people and, like Hume, he considers it to be of limited effectiveness. The reason of order, as one of the oldest reasons for proving the existence of God, has always received special attention in religion. It has been owners and thinkers. Moreover, it has always been the subject of serious attention by critics of God's belief. Immanuel Kant, although he was a critic of this reason, believed that this reason has a unique feature among other theistic reasons: "This argument always deserves to be remembered with respect. This argument is the oldest, clearest and most compatible with the common wisdom of mankind. The simple form of the reason for order is as follows: the world represents order; order requires the existence of a moderator; Therefore, the world requires the existence of a moderator.

The defenders of the reason for order have explained it in different ways, the most important explanations are: explanation based on allegorical method, explanation based on proof method, explanation based on induction method, frequency method and statistical method, they say based on calculations. Statistically, the probability that the world is the product of random and mechanical processes is small, and the probability that the world is the product of science and intelligent and purposeful creative planning is very high. But philosophers such as Nancy Cartwright and Alvin Plantinga have argued that statistical or frequency methods are not effective for studying and examining metaphysical issues such as the existence of God. Also, in Leibniz's view, God is both the generative cause and the remaining cause. It means that not only did he create the world in the beginning, but all the creatures in the world of creation need and depend on him from moment to moment, and according to him, the flow of creation is not a finished event, but a continuous process that must be maintained at every moment.

Hume's rejection of the "argument of order"

Question: Is it true that "Hume" was able to disprove the "Argument of Order"?

Hume believes that the "proof of order" has an "experimental" nature and we have not experienced the emergence of the whole world and its features to be able to say that there is a wise and powerful creator behind them.

Criticism: The need for order to regulate is the rule of reason, and in order to understand the knowledge and constructive ability of a phenomenon, there is no need to experience similar phenomena.

Hume says: Matter may have a source or origin of order in its essence.

Criticism: The inherent effect of matter does not lead to order in the entirety of a phenomenon.

Hume says: With the argument of order, it is not possible to consider the existing system as a "perfect system" and its creator as perfect. Argument of order does not require "monotheism". Unpleasant events of nature (evil) are not compatible with the order of the world. The "allegorical" reasoning of order requires and results in the "limitation" and "humanity" of God.

Criticism: These problems arise from the fact that Hume is unaware of the limits of the application of the "argument of order". He thought that all theological issues are based on one argument, and that is the "argument of order".

Detailed answer:

David Hume's objection to the proof of order

"David Hume", the English philosopher of the 18th century, believed that the allegorical expression of the "Argument of Order" has serious problems and is not able to prove the God desired by religious people. That is, when we argue that the world and its phenomena must have a knowledgeable and capable creator, just like the objects and devices made by a human being, we are actually using an argument that cannot describe God with all the considered attributes and characteristics. Prove the believers. In the second and fifth chapters of his famous book, "Dialogues concerning Natural Religion", Hume introduced several problems to the allegorical argument of order, which makes the effectiveness of the "argument of order" very limited.

In summary, those problems are:

1- Empirical nature of the proof of order: Hume believes that the "proof of order" has an empirical nature. Based on this, he says: "All arguments in the proof of order go back to experience. The fact that we judge that a stone falls, a fire burns, and the earth has unity and coherence, is because we have observed and experienced these things thousands of times with our external senses. When we see a new example, we immediately judge as always."

Hume believes that: analogy and experience are very weak in the "argument of order". In other words, the allegory in "argument of order" is an incomplete allegory; Because the similarity between "experienced things" and "the whole universe" is not certain. Because until now, we have not seen and experienced the emergence of the whole world and its

characteristics and how, so that we can conclude from seeing the phenomena of the world that there is a wise and powerful creator behind them.

Hume believed: if we see a house, we conclude with complete certainty that it was built by an architect or a builder; But we certainly cannot accept that the world is like a house so that we can infer the same cause with the same certainty. In short, the proof of order is based on the loose method of allegory and simile; Parable and likening the world to a man-made product. However, this argument is not based on human artefacts, and therefore does not have the conditions of an empirical argument; Because it has never been tested in anything other than this world. When we compare a watch and the human eye, although both of them are similar in terms of complexity and performing certain actions, this similarity is very minor and unclear; And hence, any conclusion based on the similarity of these two will be vague and dumb.

Criticism: Hume thought that the "proof of order" has an empirical nature. Let's see now; Is reasoning about the existence of the intelligent regulator through the world order an "experimental argument"? Before we get into the nature of the "argument of order", it is necessary to examine the nature of another common argument that Hume considers 100% empirical and considers the argument of order to be something like it.

We continuously learn about a man's intellect, intelligence, science and thought from his works and artifacts. Is the discovery of a man's intellect, intelligence and science through the observation of his productions an "experimental proof" or a "rational argument"?

The truth is that finding out the reason and intelligence in humans from their works and artifacts is not a logical allegory and empirical argument, but a kind of intellectual argument.

If we see written on a piece of paper: "Glory be to God Almighty, whose obedience leads to closeness, and thanks to His grace, more blessings", the possibility that all these letters were made by chance is so weak that it is unimaginable. Undoubtedly, common sense dictates that a human being - with great intelligence and taste - wrote this sentence. This is where we say: Arguing from human works on the existence of reason and thought is a type of intellectual argument, not empirical; Let alone the "argument of order" that is established about the world and its creator.

In short, there is a rational relationship between the order of a phenomenon and the involvement of consciousness in it. That is, the need of order for the organizer and designer is the rule of reason, and if it is assumed that a person has not observed any human creation, he still acknowledges its designer by observing the surprising order of nature. Therefore, in

order to find out the knowledge, intelligence, and creative ability of a phenomenon, there is no need to observe and experience similar phenomena.

2- The inherent order of matter: Hume says: What is wrong with attributing the order evident in the world to the essence of matter and not to another order. Matter may in its essence have a source or source of order. It is not possible to generalize the order resulting from the human mind - which is a small part of the world - to the order of the entire universe and say that the order of the world originates from the same source of intelligence and mind. How can a law that is fixed for a small part of the universe be generalized for the whole universe? In fact, we do not know whether the whole universe obeys the law of the small world or not? And this matter is far beyond the reach of our human perceptive powers. For example, when we see a man-made clock, by studying its details and intricacies, we realize that such an order originates outside of that clock, that is, from the intelligent and knowledgeable mentality of a human being; But this phenomenon is only a very small part of nature and maybe the order governing other natural phenomena originated not from an existence outside of those phenomena but from the essence of those phenomena.

Criticism: It should be noted that the basis of the proof of order is the coordination and cooperation between the parts of every being to achieve a specific goal, which indicates the intervention of consciousness in the composition of these parts; And the inherent characteristic of each of the elements cannot justify this type of order. In fact, this opinion requires the effect of individual components, not coherence and harmony, nor the provision of a specific goal, while in the world, in addition to the inherent effects of matter, we feel and touch a kind of comprehensive harmony and coherence. The problem of Hume's speech comes from the fact that he does not pay attention to the fact that the intrinsic effect that matter can have does not lead to the harmony and order that we can observe in the entirety of a phenomenon, and for the emergence of such Order requires a consciousness outside of that phenomenon.

3- Failure to prove the perfections of God: the allegorical reasoning of order will not prove the perfections of God; That is, it is not possible to prove the glory and beauty of God with this argument. Hume says that by relying on the argument of order, God cannot be considered immune from any errors and inconsistencies in his actions. At least you have to accept that - according to our limited vision - determining: "Does this system contain any significant defects or not?" it is impossible

Hume's point is that maybe the existing and visible problems in nature are the black exercises of an incomplete creator who is learning and practicing. Because the proof of order does not

have the ability to prove the "presumed intelligent creator", as a result of this proof, it is a creator with infinite knowledge, intelligence and ability.

Hume gives an example and says that if the noble poem of a famous poet is read to an illiterate villager, can this villager deny that the poem is completely perfect or can he even assert that it has full validity among human products? Is? Because, according to the assumption, he has never seen such poems. So it is not certain that this universe is the most complete form of the universe. Because we have no experience of any other world. When we think of a ship, we imagine the great mind of a carpenter who created such a complex, useful and beautiful machine. But if we understand that he was a childish person who imitated others and copied from another's art and in a long process and after many trials and errors, many corrections and many prototypes, he gradually completed it and came into being. Bring, will it still be a surprise for us? Based on this, it is possible that there have been many worlds, and this world is one of the best worlds, which has gradually been made into our current world through trial and error and many modifications and changes.

Hume finally wants to bring us to the question, what is the reason that the existing system is a complete system? We have never seen anything like it to compare the current version of the world. In general, before this world is built, what do we know, maybe its creator has tested the world many times until he was able to finally create such a product.

Criticism: This problem arises from the fact that Hume is unaware of the limits of the application of the "argument of order". He thought that all theological issues are based on one argument, and that is the "argument of order". Hume should have paid attention to the fact that in examining the proofs of theology, each proof includes a specific range of knowledge about God Almighty.

In these forms, Hume has established a connection between "the implication of the proof of order" and "the completeness of the existing system"; While the "completeness of the system" has nothing to do with the "proof of order". The mission of this argument is nothing more than to prove the existence of a purpose in the world and the refusal of a small device like the eye to appear by accident, is proof that there is knowledge and power at the origin of the world, and that a knowing and capable agent has created the world. Now whether the completeness and flawlessness of his act is proven or not. He has never taken on the argument of the order of proving the description of his verb (being complete). In fact, such issues can be investigated with a series of other proofs; And assuming that it cannot be investigated with other proofs and that it is one of the issues that will remain unknown to mankind forever, it does not reduce the value of the "Proof of Order".

4- Failure to prove the unity of God and other divine attributes: Hume says: How can one prove the unity of God through the allegorical argument of order? An allegorical statement does not imply that God is one. Many people work together to build a house or a ship and a car; Why can't it be assumed that multiple gods have created such a world by combining their science, design and innovation? Incidentally, such an assumption is more similar to human artefacts. In addition, this argument does not indicate the perfect attributes that God worshipers attribute to God, such as justice, mercy, etc.

Criticism: Hume's mistake here is that he thought that those who believed God to be absolute and infinite perfection found such a belief by relying on the "argument of order".

As we said in the answer to the previous forms, this English philosopher imagined that the meaning of the proof of order is the proof of the comprehensive God of all perfections and attributes of perfection. While the proof of order does not prove any other attribute for him other than proving that he is an intelligent and knowledgeable administrator. [Proof] Is this moderator obligatory or possible? Is it one or many? Is it limited or unlimited? It is beyond the scope of this argument.

5- The issue of disasters and evil: Hume said: In nature, there are unpleasant events; Such as hurricanes, earthquakes and other natural disasters that are not compatible with the issue of world order and the wisdom of the Creator.

6- It requires analogy and humanism: In addition to the above problems, Hume deals with the consequences of "the allegorical argument of order" and concludes that: first, "the allegorical argument of order" requires the "finiteness" of God's attributes; Because the cause must be consistent with the effect, and the effect is not unlimited as far as we understand. Hume believes that the order argument, besides being too weak to prove God, strongly leads to the belief of the complete "theory of anthropomorphism". The humanization of God means that God is described by the attributes of man, with the same meaning and concept as they are described to man. It is obvious that such an attribution is considered as a defect of God in the religious belief, and it is invalid.

Criticism of the above two forms: As it was said before, expecting this argument to answer all monotheistic teachings is a misplaced expectation. In the "Argument of Order", we only want to prove the existence of a God who is intelligent, wise, omniscient and capable; But "what is the level of this intelligence, reason, knowledge and power?", cannot be proven by this argument. Proving the positive and negative attributes of excellence and providing a solution to the evil problem requires proofs and arguments that are presented elsewhere.

David Hume

David Hume, born on May 7, 1711 - died on August 25, 1776, is a Scottish Enlightenment philosopher, historian, economist, librarian and Scottish essayist. Today, Hume is known more than anything else for his philosophical thoughts that were against most philosophers and had a different mindset in the field of empiricism, skepticism, and metaphysical naturalism. In fact, he should be considered one of the most famous figures in philosophy with the ideology of empiricism.

In a treatise on human nature (1740-1739 AD), Hume tried to obtain a naturalistic understanding of man in order to evaluate the psychological basis of human nature. He was against the existence of nature and believed that all human knowledge comes only from experience. This belief places him as an empiricist alongside philosophers such as: Francis Bacon, Thomas Hobbes, John Locke and George Barclay, empiricist philosophers. One of the most important enduring issues that he researched and remained in history: the issue of induction in the science of logic. Induction means that drawing any causal inference from past experiences requires assuming that the future will be like the past; An assumption that cannot be based on past experiences.

Hume argued that induction and belief in causality cannot be rationally justified and that these two arise from custom and mental habit. In fact, we never understand that one event is the result of another event (cause and effect), but we only experience "constant conjunction between events". The issue of induction here means that establishing any causal relationship from past experience requires the assumption that the future will be similar to the past, while this assumption itself cannot be established based on past experience. Hume, who was among the opponents of philosophical rationalism, believed that "passions" govern human behavior, not reason. It is famous that he said: the intellect is merely a slave of human desires, which means that the intellect is subject to human desires and has no authority over itself.

Hume was a sentimentalist philosopher and believed that morality is based more on emotion than on abstract moral principles. Hume considered himself committed to the naturalistic explanation of the moral phenomenon and is usually considered the first person who clearly explained the issue of "is and ought". The idea that is raised in this issue is that the obligation and should (ought) cannot be simply extracted from what is (is). Hume denied that human beings have a real understanding of "self" and believed that we only experience "a patch of emotions" and "the self" is nothing more than this patch full of causal perceptions. Hume's compatibilist theory of agency sees causal determinism as completely compatible with human freedom. Hume's views on the philosophy of religion, including the denial of miracles and

the denial of the order argument for the existence of God, became extremely controversial in his time. When he was accused of atheism, he said, "I must say that I accept my disbelief. In 1752, Hume became the librarian of the College of Advocates. This job was important in the sense that he had a lot of study resources at his disposal and it was at this time that he thought of writing the history of England. Hume himself saw this work as a unique work, however, after its publication, he faced strong criticism from different sections of the society. In this book, this outstanding author tries to prove the superiority of the conservatives over the liberals and the superiority of the Scots over the English. This book can also be considered as one of Hume's misfortunes, and this failure was so great for Hume that he himself said: "If there had not been a war between England and France, I would have become a refugee in France and even adopted a different name!", with all this Hume He was not discouraged and started writing the second volume of English history. Hume was influential on the schools of utilitarianism, logical positivism, philosophy of science, analytical philosophy, cognitive science, theology and many other fields and thinkers. Immanuel Kant mentions Hume as someone who awakened him from the sleep of dogmatism.

David Hume was also a philosopher and mathematician in addition to his future works and activities.

Life

David Hume was born in 1711 in Edinburgh, Scotland. His family wanted him to become a judge; But he was very interested in literature. At first he went to Bristol on business; But he gave it up very soon and went to France and started researching and thinking in the field of philosophy. During the years 1734-1737, when he lived in France, he wrote his great work on human nature. He returned to Scotland in 1737 and published another philosophical work there. In 1745, he requested to take the chair of teaching ethics and philosophy of soul at the University of Edinburgh; But his request was not accepted because he was famous for doubt and atheism. After a year of private tutoring as an army secretary, he went abroad and did not return to his country until 1749. During this period, several philosophical works were published by him, which brought him a great name and fame. In 1752, Hume became the librarian of the College of Advocates in Edinburgh and settled in that city with his sister. Using the resources available in the library, Hume turned to writing the history of England and published several volumes of it until 1761. In 1763, he went to Paris with Earl Avhertfred, the British ambassador to France, and worked as the secretary of the embassy for a while. In Paris, he socialized with a number of French philosophers; But after some time he returned to London. There, he was chosen as deputy minister for two years and in 1769, he returned to Edinburgh again. He had a great influence on philosophers after him like Kant.

[8] Kant writes in the book Preliminaries: "I admit that it was David Hume's warning that many years ago, first woke me up from the sleep of dogmatism and led me to my researches in the realm of theoretical philosophy. Give another direction.

In the book History of Civilization by Will Durant, it is said about Hume's death:

On the verge of his death, Bazul persistently asked if he now believed in another life. Hume replied: I do not know a more foolish idea than the eternity of man. Bazul persisted and asked if believing in the afterlife is not pleasant? Hume replied: "Of course, it is very sad." This time, his wife came to him and begged him to believe in God, and he joked about it. This was repeated many times and Hume refused; He died a few moments later.

Priorities and differences of taste have severely damaged this issue; For example, it has been seen in a society that the ancient people of Syria were not willing to eat pigeon meat at the height of famine and hardship. Or, for example, it is declared halal to eat chicken meat on "Thursdays", but eating the same meat on Fridays is haram, so no matter what I look at, I see that there is no clear reason for this, and it is respect or pity for no reason that I do not see a reason for.

opinions

Religion

Refusal to accept religion and religious beliefs during the time of the prophets was usually due to the inexplicable or ridiculousness of miracles, but today I do not think that a wise person can have even one suitable reason to explain religion. There are many contradictions in the Bible, which may be one of the reasons for the loss of many parts of the Bible after the death of Christ and its rewriting by a large number of apostles. But the main issue is that when a person acts based on his sense of humanity, which is a strong sense in his being, there is no need to look for weaker justifications such as ancient, historical or holy scriptures, which are full of conflicts and contradictions; Therefore, it is very selfish and inhumane for religions to expect me to follow them, while I consider the only way for human salvation to be "learning based on wisdom and objective evidence" in order to remove and end the domination of superstitions from my life forever. Look at human history, "law" has always been something variable. However, there may be fixed parts in it that have preserved it. But issues such as unsettled business conditions, war, the rule of religions in different countries, weather conditions, and especially the morality of the majority of society, have always caused changes in laws. In his book Natural History of Religion, Hume considers the origin

of monotheism among mankind to be "reason" and the origin of polytheism to fear and some other instincts.

Negation of the existence of Wajib

1. Nothing is proven unless its contradiction requires a contradiction.
2. Nothing distinctly conceivable entails a contradiction.
3. Imagining any existing object as non-existent does not require logical refusal.
4. So there is no existence whose non-existence requires a contradiction. [15] [source needed]

In the book of discourses on natural religion, Hume expresses his criticism of Cleanthes as follows: Cleanthes said: I will not leave it to Philo to show the weakness of this metaphysical reasoning for Demia. In my eyes, this reasoning is so obviously false, and at the same time, it has so little consequence for true religion and piety that I myself will dare to show its fallacy.

I will begin by stating that there is a paradox in the claim to unequivocally prove a fact by a priori evidence (non-empirical propositions). Nothing can be proven beyond doubt unless its opposite implies a contradiction. Nothing distinctly conceivable implies a contradiction. Whatever we imagine as existing, we can also imagine it as imperishable; Therefore, there is no existence whose absence implies a contradiction, and consequently there is no existence whose existence can be proved beyond doubt. They claim that the god of a being necessarily exists and they try to explain this necessity of his existence by assuming that if we know his whole essence or nature, we will definitely find his absence so impossible that two times two cannot be four, but it can be seen as long as the powers of We, who are now, remain like this can never happen. It will still be possible for us to imagine the absence of something that we imagined existed before. The mind cannot be under the necessity to assume the constant existence of an object in existence, as under It is necessary for us to always think of two multiplied by two as four. According to this phrase, necessary existence has no meaning, or in other words, it has no meaning that it deserves.

According to Hume, a claim is indisputable if it does not have empirical components or we do not need to refer to experience for the truth of that proposition, like mathematical propositions.

Of course, in Hume's critique, it is said that it is not possible to imagine an existing object as a non-existent object. Yes, it can be said that an object has been destroyed in the world of belief and mind, but an existing object can never be destroyed in reality and outside, because it is of two types outside, or its existence is dependent on its own existence. He is or his

existence is dependent on something else. If his existence is dependent on his own essence, such as *Wajib*, the essence of an object cannot be separated from it, then it always exists. Obligatory means there is a cause, there is an effect, or the possible object, and it was said that the existence of the obligatory does not disappear, so the possible does not disappear either.

Criticism of the Argument of Order

Unlike the order argument itself, its criticism does not go back to the distant past. Although denial of purposefulness and regularity can also be seen in Epicurus's thoughts, the first serious criticisms of this argument were often the result of David Hume's work.

Regarding the description of the general harmony in the world, Hume in his book *Conversations on Natural Religion* from the language of Philo said that it must be acknowledged that it is impossible for us, from the limited view we have, to say whether this system, compared to possible and even actual systems Does it contain any significant errors or not? According to him, if a farmer and a farmer, if the poem of Anhed was recited to him, could he consider that poem completely free of errors and mistakes? He had never seen any other poem in his life.

Hume says that the analogy used in Pili's presentation of the argument of order is very loose and weak; And the empirical analogy is only valid between two empirical phenomena, not between an experimental phenomenon and a non-empirical phenomenon; We have learned through experience that human artifacts are the result of planning, but we do not have such experience with natural collections.

In simpler terms, this argument assumes that between natural objects (such as the eye) and artificial objects (such as a watch), there is an important and meaningful similarity, and this is despite the fact that it is not clear that the human eye is similar to a watch in any significant way. be While the allegorical argument is based on the assumption that there is a significant similarity between the parties of the allegory. If this similarity is faint or weak, the results based on this comparison will be equally weak. Based on this, for example, a wristwatch and a pocket watch are so similar that we are allowed to believe that both of them were created by watchmakers, but despite the fact that there are similarities between watches and eyes (both are complicated and do their own special things); This similarity is insignificant, and in the same proportion, any kind of conclusion based on this analogy will be insignificant.

Hume showed that the argument of order can at best prove that the phenomena of the world are made by someone or something or those or things; It means that it is unable to prove

monotheism. It is not against the possibility that a group of inferior gods have planned this world in cooperation. Especially if we use an allegory, considering that complex human artifacts such as skyscrapers and space rockets, etc., are the result of the work of groups of people; We cannot conclude monotheism.

Criticism of causality argument

Hume claims that the ratio of cause and effect forms the acute and urgent concept of all our thinking about real things; So we should raise questions about it and try to understand it instead of assuming that we know its meaning. Hume divided all human perceptions into two groups: impressions and ideas.

Hume means by "impressions" the direct data of sense and experience. Like opening our eyes and seeing a natural scene. What he means by "perceptions" is the renewal of the same perceptions after the direct sensory relationship has been cut off, with the help of imagination and memory. He then divides the relationship between impressions and perceptions into two groups: natural relationship and philosophical relationship. What Hume means by "natural relation" is establishing the association of meanings between two ideas in the mind; So that when one emerges, another emerges immediately.

What he means by "philosophical ratio" is a relationship that results from comparing two or more things with each other, without necessarily transferring the mind from one to the other through the connection and association of meanings.

Hume divides "natural proportions" into three groups:

1. Similarity ratio (in English: Resemblance)
2. Continuity in time or place in English
3. Cause and effect ratio in English: Cause and Effect

In all the three mentioned qualities, there is this feature that their imagination leads to the other through the natural force of association and connection; And based on nature or habit, the idea of one creates another idea in the mind. Hume believes that the mentioned natural link between ideas should be limited to the world of mind and perceptions and should not be attributed to the outside world and say that the same relations exist between external beings. Hume divides "philosophical relations" into seven groups:

1. The ratio of similarity or similarity is the ratio of sameness
2. Temporal and spatial relationship

3. Quantitative or numerical fit
4. Degrees of quality
5. Conflict ratio
6. Cause and effect ratio

Hume then says that each of the above seven philosophical ratios are not out of two states:

1. Ratios dependent on our perceptions, which include: "similarity ratio", "quantitative or numerical ratio", "quality degrees" and "conflict ratio". Our understanding of these matters is certain.
2. Ratios independent of our imaginations, which include: "Identity ratio", "time and space ratio", and "cause and effect ratio". According to Hume, our knowledge of such things is possible and we cannot achieve certain knowledge.

According to Hume, continuous and continuous repetition of everyday phenomena are responsible for the emergence of "identity ratio", "temporal and spatial ratio", and "cause and effect ratio" in our mind.

For example, when we experience fire, we also feel heat, and the repetition of this experience causes us to expect the appearance of heat in our minds when we see fire; Therefore, the relationship of causality is nothing but the association of meanings and mental expectation caused by the repetition of experience and continuous succession or symmetry.

Based on this, Hume considers the relationship of causality to be nothing more than a mental habit that results from the experience of frequent temporal-spatial continuity of two events. Hume states that the relationship of causality is neither self-evident and intuitive, nor based on rational argument; Rather, it is an empirical rule, and to prove that this rule is empirical, he says: causes and effects are not known by reason and are discovered only through experience. Therefore, no definite and necessary predictions about future events can be made.

Hume tries to gather evidence to negate the relationship of causation. He writes about this:

If something is revealed to someone who has a lot of intellectual power, if that thing is completely new to him, even with careful experiments on its perceptible qualities, he cannot obtain anything from its causes or effects... Adam, who is supposed to The beginning of the intellect was perfect, he could never infer its drowning by observing the flow and softness of the water or find out by observing the light and heat of the fire that it burns him.

Hume wrote in a treatise that any inductive reasoning is based on the concept of causality, and on the other hand, this concept itself is based on the criterion of induction; That is, all empirical conclusions are based on the assumption that the future is the same as the past, and therefore all the connections we have found between events today or in the past will also be used in the future, and the causes that have caused effects in the past will also be the same in the future. Hume, calling experience the only support, rejected the use of experience to establish general principles and called the foundation of causation an unjustified generalization, arguing that there was no experience of the future. You have experienced the stone falling to the ground many times, but you have never experienced that it always falls to the ground. You see the earth and the stone and understand its fall, but you do not understand the force that pulls the stone towards the earth. You have never experienced that law yourself. The experience has only been that things fall to the ground. You are sure that the stone will fall, because you have seen this event many times; You are used to these two being together, and then you rule over the law. Hume used two billiard balls as an example. If a black ball is rolled and hits a stationary white ball, the white ball will move. In this case, the verdict is usually due to causation; That is, the impact of the black ball is considered the cause of the movement of the white ball. Hume argued that the motion of the white sphere is experienced but the actual cause of its motion is not experienced; In fact, the ruling of causation has been for the fact that one event occurred after another event; But causality has not been tested. Hume emphasized that the expectation of something coming after something else is not in those things themselves; Rather, it is in the human mind. Expecting the movement of the white ball in collision with the black ball, not inherent; Rather, it is acquired. In short, David Hume considered the causal connection to be a psychological connection and not a logical connection. He believed that in all cases where people believe in causality, they have reached this belief only because of the succession or symmetry of two phenomena in the outside world; Therefore, it is never possible to determine causality in external objects.

Aesthetics

Hume's two important treatises on aesthetics are "On the Criterion of Taste" and "On Tragedy".

About the criterion of taste

Hume developed the idea of "taste" that emerged from the dominant eighteenth-century thinking about art. By discussing about taste, and not about the beauty or appropriateness of the object, the thinkers of this period changed the focus of thinking about art from the quality of the work to the experience of the viewer, listener, or reader, and the way to discuss about

"aesthetic experience", and Also, later they opened "Aesthetic properties". In his essay "On the Criteria of Taste", David Hume traces an attempt to reconcile two apparently contradictory concepts. On the one hand, the difference in tastes seems obvious. "What you think is truly wonderful may be horrifying or even disgusting to me!" This is true for art as well, although it is also true for something like ice cream. Taste is a matter of emotions, of how I feel about things. Hume reconciles the two different positions by stating that there are, in fact, criteria for taste. These criteria represent a general consensus derived from experience about "common human feelings". The reason for rejecting the taste of each person alone follows the same criteria; In the words of Hume, "These refining emotions of the mind, originate from a very sensitive and delicate nature, and they need a consensus of very favorable conditions for planning their play (meaning the use of imagination) by the innate talent, based on their general and established principles, such as A machine, the least external obstruction to its little springs, or the least internal irregularity, destroys their motion, and disturbs the operation of the whole machine. Therefore, although he is right to some extent that "beauty is in the eye of the beholder", but despite that, Hume believes that "nature has established a comprehensive and common beauty as a link between form and emotions". Hume proposes two tests to recognize the work of art. The first test is the test of time, which does not seem very suitable for new works; This test holds that what has been recognized by many generations of art appreciators as a great work of art must be considered great because common human emotions confirm it. Hume's second test is not really a test, but more of a recommended method for art critics and appraisers.

1. Start with the right tools: It takes a sensitive imagination to reliably detect the "sense of beauty."
2. Repetition [practice] evolves: more experience in viewing works of art leads to more insightful judgment.
3. Adopt multiple perspectives: What is missed on the first review may be found on the third or fourth.
4. Comparing the work with other similar works: This action helps to see what may be lost due to ignoring this method.
5. Freeing the mind from prejudices: as much as possible, any special personal interest that may arise against the work should be forgotten. For example, because the creator of the work is one of your relatives, or because you paid a lot of money for it, or you agree or disagree with the content or components of the work; It is better to try to be an impartial observer.

It is not easy to agree with all these descriptions; That is why, according to Hume, "a true judge of art is a rare person". However, such judges can be found, as a result of which their verdicts are a criterion for criticism. "A strong sense united with sensitive affections, the raising of artistic insight by repetition in observation, the evolution by comparison, and the freedom from all prejudice, can make critics dub this valuable quality; And such a common rule, wherever it is found, is the true criterion of taste and beauty. Although one might think that critical judgment is too highly subjective, Hume argues that the judgments of such critics are valid only where they are corroborated by other observers, and since the basis of the standard of taste is the comprehensive human emotions. is, there will be a tendency for others to agree with the critical judgment. [Now] think about whether this is true, or how true it can be, and how much you think taste is a culturally defined matter, or a class-based matter. Hume ends his essay with two observations on this matter. He states that any debate about the merits of a work of art cannot be resolved by the criterion of taste. There is a natural variation in feelings, such as why some people desire what others do not desire. Hence, a young person may prefer romantic stories, and an old person may prefer philosophy. No criterion is used here; One taste is not better than another, it's just a kind of difference. A similar issue is also true in some cases, where taste changes from one culture to another. What is funny to an American may not be funny to a Korean, and vice versa. This is really a matter of cultural differences, and there are no cross-cultural truths about what is truly funny.

About tragedy

Hume begins the essay with the question "how is tragedy still pleasurable in spite of the painful and unfortunate reactions it evokes?". This issue leads him to focus on the subject of tragedy and its relationship with passivities. Until now, Hume's opinion about this relationship has been formulated in various ways, one of the most famous of which is Hume's transformation hypothesis. Based on this hypothesis, unfortunate passivities are transformed into pleasurable passivities due to the stylistic and rhetorical arrangements of tragedy. This hypothesis has undergone many confirmations, denials, corrections and changes over the years and has had its supporters and opponents. But in most cases, the supporters and opponents of this hypothesis agree that tragedy produces pleasure through poetic and rhetorical devices.

Moral philosophy

Beauty and ugliness are purely subjective and do not exist in the real world. Moral nature did not exist in humans and does not exist. What has led mankind to this direction (the existence of moral principles) is only a general conclusion obtained from partial examples and what is

the truth is our feeling, not a moral value. According to Hume, the philosophy of ethics is not philosophy at all and is purely emotional in origin. He says somewhere: It will be logically justified if I destroy the world so that my hand does not get scratched, but this action and decision is devoid of emotions. As a result, he does not accept moral philosophy to a large extent (not completely because it was the benefit of belief).

Russell's opinion about Hume

Bertrand Russell says in the book History of Western Philosophy that Hume's philosophy literally leads us to a dead end and the issues and questions raised by Hume still remain unanswered. Russell considers Hume's most important work to be the Treatise of Human Nature. Hume has a book titled "History of England" which was published in 1755. In this book, Hume tries to prove the superiority of the conservatives over the liberals and the superiority of the Scots over the English. Hume did not consider history to be a place of philosophical disinterestedness

A translation based on the parable of the reason of order

The most famous form of explanation is the order of explanation based on an allegory, which was presented by William Paley in his book titled Natural Theology or Reasons for God's Existence and Attributes from the Manifestations of Nature.

Paley's first exposition of the reason for order is in the form of an allegory in which he compares the world to a clock. He believes that both of them have a high degree of order that can only be explained through the moderator. Of course, the clock can be explained by appealing to a human agent, but the world requires the belief in the existence of a cosmic clockmaker on a divine scale. We now examine his argument:

Imagine that while crossing a bush, my foot hit a stone, if I were asked how the stone got there, I could probably answer that as far as I know it has been there forever, maybe a sign. It is not easy to give the unreasonableness of this answer. But suppose I find a watch that has fallen on the floor. And to find out how the clock got there, the previous answer cannot be given - for all I know, the clock may have been there forever. But why can't the answer that is used for the stone be used for the watch? Why is the second case not as acceptable as the first case? The only reason is that when we examine the watch we find (what we couldn't find in the stone) that its many parts are fitted together for a purpose. such as that they are so formed and arranged as to cause motion, and that the motion is so regular as to indicate time, that if the various parts were formed in a form other than what they are, if their size were different

from their present size, or were placed in a different order other than the current state, in that case either no movement would be performed in the device at all, or it would not have the function it has now. From this obvious mechanism (in fact, this mechanism requires the investigation of the tool and perhaps the previous knowledge of the subject to understand and understand it; as we have said, as soon as such an orderly entity is observed and understood), we think that this conclusion is inevitable. is, that the watch must have had an existing watchmaker, and that some time and place some craftsman or craftsmen fashioned it for the purpose we really find it to answer; Those who understood its building and designed its use.

Paley completes the parable by considering the world. The order of the world, like the order of the clock, logically requires the acceptance of a master craftsman or master of the world.

Hume (1711-1776) in his book *Dialogues on Natural Religion*, explains the explanation based on the allegory of the argument of order (which, of course, he himself does not accept) as follows:

Look around the world; Think about the whole world and every part of it; You will find it nothing but a great device that explains more detailed divisions beyond what human senses and powers can explain; Accepts. All these numerous devices, even their smallest components, have been carefully coordinated with each other that all humans who have thought about it so far; It amazes. The amazing fit of means with ends, throughout nature, is exactly like and even beyond the product of human creativity, the product of human design, thought, wisdom and intelligence. Therefore, because the effects are similar to each other, through the rules of analogy, we are led to the conclusion that the causes are also similar, and the creator of nature is something similar to the human mind; Although he has much greater powers that are in line with the magnificence of the work he has accomplished. With this a posteriori argument, and with this argument alone, can we prove the existence of God and its similarity with the human mind and intelligence?

The allegorical argument of order presented by Hume can be summarized as follows:

- (1) The world is like a machine.
- (2) Similar effects prove similar causes.
- (3) As disabilities, the world and devices are similar to each other.
- (4) Therefore, the causes of the world and devices are similar to each other.
- (5) Therefore, the creator of nature has attributes that are similar to and even greater than the human mind.

3. Hume's objections to the explanation based on the allegory of the reason for order

Paley's argument has been attacked even before him, as David Hume (1711-1776) long before that in his famous book *Dialogues Concerning Natural Religion*, published in 1779, raised traditional objections to the order argument. It seems that Paley was not aware of them.

David Hume believed that the allegorical expression of the reason for order has serious problems and is not able to prove the desired God of religious people. In the second and fifth chapters of the book *Conversations about Natural Religion*, he has introduced many problems to the allegorical reasoning of order, which makes the effectiveness of reason of order seem very limited. The summary of those problems is given here:

The first form: the empirical nature of the proof of order: Hume believes that the proof of order is empirical in nature. Based on this, he says: All arguments for the reason of order go back to experience. While it is not possible to make this definite and infallible conclusion from experience. The fact that we judge that stone falls, fire burns, and the earth has unity and cohesion is because we have observed and experienced thousands of times, so when a new example of this nature comes upon us. It is supplied without delay, we do the usual inference. The exact similarity of the cases gives us a complete certainty of a similar event, after which we do not look for a stronger reason.

Hume believed that allegory is very weak in the argument of order. In other words, he considered the allegory in order reasoning to be an incomplete allegory because he did not consider the similarity between the things experienced and the whole universe to be known and taken for granted. He says: If we see a house, we conclude with full certainty that it was built by an architect or a builder. Because this is what we have experienced all kinds of these effects, which causes it to exist. But surely we cannot accept that the world is like a house so that we can infer the same cause with the same certainty. What exists here is a guess, possibility and assumption that there is a similar cause.

Hume says that man's awareness of the obvious does not enable him to determine what kind of situation the world should be. Because none of those things that he did not understand can be considered impossible. Also, before the experience, it is impossible to determine the cause of the accident or the cause of the universe. However, it can be raised as a possibility against other possibilities. But there will never be a convincing statement for the preference of one of them over the others. Only experience can show us the correct cause of any phenomenon. Therefore, we do not know anything prior to experience, we do not advance any knowledge

we don't have

In the case of allegorical arguments, the main concern is with regard to the strength or weakness of the allegory. As Hume noted, this argument is based on the principle that similar effects prove similar causes. Therefore, the more similarities between the effects are seen, the stronger the argument for the causes that are not seen; It will be more. As Hume puts it:

But still to show you more problems in your anthropomorphic view [attributing human attributes to God], please do a new research in your principles. Similar effects prove similar causes.

How can a law that is fixed for a small part of the universe be generalized for the whole universe? Is there any reasonable reason that the inhabitants of other planets have thought, intelligence, reason or anything like human powers? When nature has so much diversity, can it be concluded from the way it works in this small part of the earth that it is the same in all other parts of the universe? Can we be sure that thought and reason similar to human thought and reason can be found in the whole universe and its activity is much more and beyond the activity that appears for us in this part of the world? A very small part of this large system in a very short time will be too incomplete for us to make inferences about the origin of the whole system. In fact, we do not know that the whole universe obeys the law of our small world. This matter is far beyond the reach of our human perceptive powers.

The third form: the explanation based on allegory requires "the theory of analogy and anthropomorphism": following the previous problems that were related to the principle of allegory, Hume deals with the consequences of the allegorical expression of order, and in summing up the argument of order as follows He concludes that: First, the allegorical reasoning (similar effects have similar causes) requires the finite nature of God's attributes, because the cause must correspond to the effect and the effect is not infinite as far as we understand. . The defender of the order argument may claim that God is not similar to humans in all attributes, which would be the most dominant hypothesis. And at the same time, it will weaken all the proofs of God's existence. Therefore, Hume believes that the proof of order based on allegory, in addition to being too weak to prove God, strongly leads to the belief of the theory of perfect anthropomorphism.

The fourth form: Allegorical reasoning is incapable of proving God's perfections: Allegorical reasoning will not prove God's perfection, and God cannot be considered immune from any mistakes and inconsistencies in his actions. There are so many inexplicable problems in the workings of nature that if we were to establish a perfect creator beforehand

These problems can be easily solved. And only in terms of the special perceptive capacity of humans, their analysis seems difficult, because our limited perceptual system cannot

recognize unlimited relationships. But according to the method of allegorical reasoning of the proponents of the argument of order, all these problems become real, and perhaps as new cases of similarity to human initiative and art, we can emphasize them, at least you have to accept that according to our limited vision, we determine that Does this system contain any significant defects or not? It is impossible. Hume gives an example and says that if the poet's poem is read to an illiterate countryman, can this countryman completely deny that the poem is perfect, or can he even emphasize that it is among the human products that have credibility? Is it perfect? Because according to the assumption, he has never seen such poems. Therefore, it is not certain that this world is the most perfect form of the world because we have no experience of any other world.

When we consider a ship, we imagine the great thought of a carpenter who created such a complex, useful and beautiful machine. But if we understand that he was a childish person who imitated others and copied from another's art and in a long process and after many trials and errors, many corrections and many prototypes, he gradually completed it. did and created, will it still be surprising for us? Therefore, it is possible that there have been many worlds, and this world is one of the best worlds, which has been gradually built into our current world through trial and error and a lot of modification and change.

The fifth form: the allegorical argument of order does not require the unity of God: Hume presents other forms here and says how can one prove the unity of God through the allegorical argument of order? An allegorical statement does not imply that God is one. Many people build a house or a ship or a car at the same time, why can't it be assumed that many gods have created such a world by combining their science, design and initiative? By the way, such an assumption is more similar to human artifacts.

The sixth form: allegorical reasoning cannot negate a human-like God: in this form, Hume says that the allegorical expression of order requires belief in a human-like God. In explaining this form, he says: Man is a mortal being and the human race reproduces by reproduction, this is the characteristic of all living beings. The two genders, male and female, keep the world alive. Therefore, the allegorical proof of order requires the extension of this fact to God or gods. Why shouldn't God or Gods be human-like? Why shouldn't they be physical and have eyes, ears, mouth and the like? Reason has not been seen in any creature except man, so gods must have a human personality. In the event that the god of gods does not have such physical attributes. Even if we accept that the world represents order, why is the assumption that the world was created by a conscious being and a designer more justified than the assumption that the world was born from the sexual union of two other worlds that are both Because they are the parents of this world; is it

4. Professor Motahari's answers to Hume's problems on the allegorical expression of order

Professor Motahari tried to defend the allegorical expression in the book "The Reasons for the Tendency to Materialism" and tried to provide convincing answers to Hume's many problems with the allegorical expression of order. In response to the first forms, contrary to Hume, he believes that the argument of order is not an empirical argument but a rational argument:

It is a mistake that Mr. Hume thought that the proof of order is of an empirical nature like all other empirical proofs. Empirical evidence is when we want to discover the relationship of a tangible phenomenon with another tangible phenomenon. In other words, empirical proof can only be valid for the discovery of the relationship between two components of nature, not for the discovery of the relationship between nature and the supernatural. In other words, experience is possible when we observe a phenomenon in nature and we want to discover the cause or causes of that phenomenon by experiment, or we want to know its effects and results. For example, with experience, we find the relationship between the heat of water and its vaporization, or the relationship between the coldness of water and its freezing. When we see two factors following each other and we are sure of the involvement of another factor, we judge that one of these two is the cause of the other. So, the condition for a relationship to be empirical is that both sides of the relationship are perceptible and under the control of our sensory observation. (Motahari, 1357: 184-5)

The question raised here is what kind of argument is the argument and what is the criterion of empiricalness or rationality of the argument? Ibn Sina in his book *Al-Najah* and Khwaja Nasir Tusi in *Tajrid al-Itqad* and Allameh Hali in his explanation in his book *Al-Jawhar al-Nazid* in the definition of proof have said that proof is an analogy that consists of certain premises that inherently and necessarily leads to a certain conclusion.

Certainty is an affirmation that is symmetrical with the refusal of its opposite. Therefore, the assertion that "A is B" will be certain if it is symmetric to "It is impossible that A is not B". Therefore, a certain theorem must be either self-evident or a theoretical theorem that leads to the self-evident theorem. Now, if these certain theorems that are used as the premises of an argument are a priori theorems, such an argument can be considered a rational argument, otherwise it will be an empirical argument. And some thinkers even consider the possibility of an empirical argument. have been denied; Al-Farabi says in the book of logic: And Al-Barhan Ali Zarbeen: I mean geometric, and I mean logical. This shows that according to him, we do not have an empirical proof, but the proof is either mathematical or logical.

Therefore, it seems that a posteriori proofs, like reasoning through order, are empirical proofs. William Roe, in his article entitled *Cosmological Argument*, divides the proofs of God's existence into two types of a posteriori proofs.

And he divides a priori proofs and says: Posterior proofs are based on a principle or theorem that we gain knowledge of through experience in the outside world - such as a cosmological proof.

The first one is based on external facts that need a cause in their existence, and the second one is based on facts that have order and harmony. A priori proofs are proofs that are based on principles that we have knowledge of independently of our experience in the world, such as ontological proofs. Therefore, the condition of an proof being empirical is that it is based on principles and facts that are after Our experience is gained in the outside world. An argument can be defined as an intellectual argument that does not require principles and facts derived from experience. Therefore, since the reason for order is based on a premise that is obtained from the outside world after our experience, it can be considered an empirical reason. As a result, as Hume claimed, the expression based on the parable is considered an empirical argument, not a rational argument.

However, Professor Motahari considers reasoning through order to be a rational argument, and in rejecting the empirical nature of the order argument, he says: "Now let's see if reasoning through the order of the world to the existence of a conscious moderator is an empirical argument? Let's look at the nature of the argument of order. It is necessary to examine the nature of another common argument which Mr. Hume considers 100% empirical and considers the argument of order to be something similar to it. And that argument and argument is based on human works and artefacts. Intellect, thought and intelligence are human beings... Is the discovery of intelligence and science of human makers from their artifacts an empirical proof or an intellectual argument? And their artefacts are neither logical as "parable" nor as empirical reasoning, but a kind of rational argument. (Mothari, 1357: 88-85). Then Professor Motahari proves through the calculation of probabilities that human works and artefacts indicate human intellect and intelligence, and he explains as follows:

When he studies their works, he always sees that among all kinds of works, but also among thousands of forms and forms of work, only one form achieves a desired result and the other forms do not. As a result, they choose the same shape and the same specific face that achieves the desired result, leaving the other shapes and faces. For example, if a person picks up a pen and wants to draw it on the paper, a black color can be drawn in a single shape, there are a thousand possible ways, one of which is, for example, in the shape of an "M". And if he

continues and draws the pen on the paper, a thousand different shapes can be drawn, one of which is "N" and if he repeats his action again, a thousand different shapes are possible, one of which is the "T" shape. If the pen is taken in hand and the shape of "Ment" becomes, in fact, it should be said that one-thousandth of the one-thousandth of the one-thousandth of the one-thousandth of the possibilities has happened. And if he continued his work and wrote a few lines, and this form appeared from their collection: "Praise be to God Almighty, whose obedience brings you nearness, and thanks to Him, more blessings, every breath that sinks in prolongs life." and when it comes to the pleasure of nature, then there are two blessings in every breath and gratitude is obligatory for every blessing... "The possibility that all these letters were made by chance and not by selection, that is, by attention and choice, is so weak. Which is unimaginable, which means that the human mind usually finds it impossible. It is from here that it is ruled that there is the power of "choice", that is, what is called reason and will. This is the problem of saying that arguing from human works and artefacts about the existence of reason and thought in them is not a logical allegory... nor is it an empirical reason... but it is a kind of intellectual argument. So it turned out that knowing us and gaining the intellect and intelligence of other human beings other than ourselves is not of the type of empirical evidence, let alone the proof of order that is established about the world and its relationship with the Supreme Being. be of the type of empirical reason."

But according to Professor Motahari's explanations, it seems that understanding the intellect and intelligence of humans through human works and artefacts from experience cannot be a rational argument, because in a rational argument one must have certain and impossible premises. doubt is used, but reasoning through the calculation of probabilities is firstly reasoning through induction and experience and secondly, it is an argument that is not certain and logical, but simply increases the probability of non-coincidence. But again, the probability of coincidence is not zero, but weak, and the absence of coincidence is not certain, so it cannot be a rational argument. If the argument from the works and artefacts of man on the existence of reason and thought is not a logical analogy or an empirical reason and is through the calculation of probabilities, then it will be empirical and not rational. In addition, reasoning through order is an a posteriori reasoning, that is, it is based on the introduction or preliminaries that are formed after our experience from the outside world. However, the criterion stated by Professor Motahari for the empirical nature of an argument, which consists of discovering the relationship between two tangible components of nature through experimentation, does not seem to be a precise criterion.

4.1. Implicit confirmation of Hume's first form by Motahari professor

Professor Motahari denies the explanation of the reason for order based on allegory and considers it impossible to have a complete similarity between human artefacts and the universe, which is the creation of the sublime. As Hume emphasized that such a similarity is not certain. He says the following in the book "The Reasons for Tendency to Materialism":

... that Mr. Hume says: This argument is a kind of "simile" in terms of its nature, and the purpose is to prove the complete similarity between the creation of nature and the creation of man, it is wrong. It is impossible that the work of the creator of nature (God) is completely similar to the work of man. Rather, the creator of nature, as in terms of essence and attributes, is distinguished by being similar to a human being, in terms of actions and works, he is also distinguished by similarity. Man is a part of nature, as he is a part of nature, he is a creature in the process of "becoming" and evolving, all his efforts are to bring himself from power to action and from imperfection to perfection. All human efforts are a kind of movement from power to action and from imperfection to perfection. And also because it is a part of nature, not the creator of nature. His possession of nature is in the form of establishing an artificial (unnatural) relationship between the parts of nature. ... So there are two things that are human-made. A) The connection of artificial components is an artificial connection and not a natural one. b) The aim and intention used in this craft is the aim and intention of the maker. That is, it is the creator who, through this artefact, achieves a goal and removes the defect from himself, and in a way, brings himself from power to actuality. None of these two elements can exist in the bari-tali industry.

As it is known from the above statement, Master Motahari rejects comparing the world to human artifacts. The non-consistency of the world's similarity to human artefacts was one of Hume's most serious criticisms (form 1), on which many of Hume's other criticisms are based. Therefore, Professor Motahari's explanation in expressing the dissimilarity of the world to human artifacts is considered as an implicit confirmation of Hume's first forms.

4.2. Professor Motahari's answer to Hume's fourth problem

Professor Motahari proposes the fourth form of Hume, which: Mr. Hume says, supposing our world is the most perfect possible world, where the creator of the world did not copy it from somewhere else, or he himself gradually and He has not completed the practice of his industry. ..." In rejecting these problems of Hume, he says: "These problems are also due to the fact that Hume is unaware of the limits of the application of the argument of order. He thinks that all theological issues are deduced from one argument, and that argument is order.

It does not seem that such an understanding of the above forms is correct, Hume never said explicitly or implicitly that all theological issues should be deduced from this argument in

order for the argument to be valid. Rather, what he means is that the proof of order based on allegory cannot be a discovery of the knowledge, power, prudence and intelligence of the controller of the universe. Moreover, Professor Motahari also believes that the proof of order does not prove the power, wisdom, and intelligence of the ruler of the world, but other proofs should be sought to prove these things. Hume's claim is that if we consider the world to be similar to human artefacts and try to prove God through allegory, then this will corrupt our allegorical reasoning. As human artefacts come to the fore after practice and gradual completion, this assumption will come to mind that maybe the world has gone through such a process.

. Professor Motahari's answer to Hume's fifth form

Professor Motahari presents Hume's fifth forms as Hume says: Suppose it is proved with this argument that the creator of the world has the intellect and intelligence of a human being. The claim that proves God's infinite perfection has not been proven. And then in rejecting Hume's problems, he says: Mr. Hume's mistake here is that those who believe that God is absolute and infinite perfection by relying on the proof of order - which according to him was an empirical proof - believe such a belief. have found (Ibid.: 195)

Of course, it seems that Hume's intention has not been properly expressed here, Hume did not have such an idea that he puts forward. And Hume's point was not that the proof of order does not prove the absolute and infinite perfection of God, but what he meant was that the proof of order based on allegory will not be compatible with the belief in the absolute and infinite perfection of God. Professor Motahari, based on his understanding of these forms of Hume, rightly points out the effectiveness of the argument of order:

"... the value of the argument of order is only to the extent that it leads us to the border of the supernatural. This argument proves as much that nature has a transcendental nature and is subject to the transcendental, and that transcendental is sensitive to the essence and He is sensitive to his actions. But whether that transcendence is obligatory or possible? Is it accidental or ancient? Is it one or many? Is it limited or unlimited? Is its knowledge and power finite or infinite? It is beyond the scope of this argument. These are issues. which is solely the responsibility of divine philosophy, and divine philosophy proves these with other proofs.

Hume also believed that the proof of order is incapable of proving these attributes, and in addition, he believed that the proof of order based on allegory is not compatible with the belief in the attributes of necessity, antiquity, unity, unlimitedness, and the infinite knowledge

of God. Therefore, Ostad Motahari's statement is considered to validate Hume's opinion about the proof of order.

From this point, it can be understood that the third form of Hume, which stated that the explanation based on allegory requires the theory of analogy and anthropomorphism, and also the sixth form of Hume, which said that the explanation based on allegory does not negate the anthropomorphic God. If the God of God is one of the human attributes of Menza; The flaws in the parable-based explanation are considered the reason for the order, and Professor Motahari implicitly and even in some phrases explicitly mentions these shortcomings of the parable-based explanation as they will be mentioned in the next paragraphs of the article; confirms

4.4. Implicit confirmation of Hume's assessment of the reason for order by Professor Motahari

In the footnote of the fifth volume of Principles of Philosophy and the Method of Realism, Professor Motahari comes very close to Hume's evaluations of the reason for order and implicitly validates many of Hume's problems and judgments about the reason for order. He divides the ways of knowing God into three types:

- 1- The way of the heart or the way of nature
- 2- The way of sense and science or the way of nature
- 3- The way of reason or the way of reasoning and philosophy

And then he divides the way of sense and science or the way of nature into three ways:

- 1- Through the organizations and systems used in the construction of the world. (the way of order) and it is clear that this way is passed through experience.
- 2- By way of mysterious guidance and guidance that creatures are on their way. (the way of guiding beings)
- 3- Through the creation of the world. (the way of creation)

1- Organizations and systems: Studying the state of beings shows that the building of the world, and the building of the units that make up the parts of the world, is "calculated", everything has a "place" and is placed for it and has a purpose. Some of these placements have been used.

However, how to understand the existence of the All-Knowing and All-Wise God from the structures and systems of the building, Professor Motahari believes that such a result can be achieved through the necessity of the correlation between the effective and the effective. He proved the existence of this Sankhit between effective and efficient uses the probability calculation method. He says that although the opposite possibility, that is, the possibility that this phenomenon is random, is not ruled out, but this opposite possibility is so weak that no common sense considers it. As it can be seen, Professor Motahari does not use the allegorical reasoning of order - just as Hume also considered the allegorical reasoning of order to be ineffective and directed his criticisms towards it - but through the contrast between the work And Mofar argues that the purposeful order of the world must be caused by the able and purposeful controller of the universe. In addition to that, Master Motahari has another way which he calls the guidance and wayfinding of beings; proposes and prefers it over the reason of order.

2- Guidance and wayfinding: Professor Motahari introduces another way as the way of sense and science or the way of nature, which can replace the reason of order as a teleological argument.

One of the signs and symptoms that can be observed in the creation of creatures, which is the proof of the intervention of some kind of intention and planning, is "finding the way" of objects. In addition to the organism and the regular internal organization, every creature has a mysterious force, thanks to which the force knows its way to the future. In other words, objects and beings, while they are blind and blind in terms of material and physical structure, a kind of mysterious vision guides them, this mysterious vision should be sought beyond the physical structure of objects. ... this reason is different from the reason of order, the reason of order is related to physical and material organization and organization, in other words, the organism of objects of an industrial device such as a car or watch or textile factory has organization, has components and It is a member and an organization, every part of it testifies that it was made for something and purposefully used in its construction, but a car or a clock or a textile factory and any other industrial unit of a special force. "Wayfinding" is not useful, there is no mysterious relationship between him and the device's goal that automatically guides him in the direction of his goal, unlike natural units that are like that. (Motahari, Principles of Philosophy and the Method of Realism, Vol. 5, pp. 64-65)

Professor Motahari says about these two ways of reasoning: The Holy Qur'an is apparently the first book that distinguishes between the internal order of things and their guidance and wayfinding, and mentions them as two reasons, that is, it has implicitly proved that the way Finding creatures is not only a result of their material and internal order and structure. Our

Lord said, "Give all the things of creation, then guide them" (Taha, verse 50), "God created the Fasu' and "Qadr Fahdi" (Aali, verses 3 and 4) and He says about the guidance of the creatures: "And revelation in the whole sky of things" (Ham Sajdah, verse 12) And the stars and the trees prostrate themselves (Al-Rahman, verse 6), and the revelation of the Lord to Al-Nahl (Nahl, verse 68), the angels are generous and pious (Shams, verse 8), and those who act in charity (Anbiya, verse 73)

Then Professor Motahari uses the term "innovation and innovation" to prove purposeful guidance in creatures, and therefore it is believed that wherever some kind of innovation is seen, it is proof of the existence of purposeful guidance. He says that a calculator may be built so regularly that it performs addition, subtraction, multiplication and division operations precisely, that is, the structural order of the machine can create such a property. But a calculator is never capable of inventing a mathematical rule... He explains about the invention and innovation in living beings as follows: In the work of vital cells, several types of innovative work can be seen that the building Their machine is not enough to justify that kind of work, or we should believe that those cells have so much intelligence, knowledge, intelligence, and understanding that humans themselves have not and will not reach their base in any way... or We have to believe that a mysterious force directly led them in their work in a way other than through reason and perception... extraordinary works that are considered "innovation" and the mechanical building of the cell. are not enough to justify them; There are several types:

-) the power to adapt to the environment and change its nature,
- 2) Division of work and task selection,
- 3) The initiative to renew the building of the missing member or to create a new member.
- 4- Discovering your needs without the mediation of teaching and learning. "

Then he quotes some phrases from the book The Secret of Human Creation and says: In the book The Secret of Human Creation, page 85 states, "Many animals such as crabs, whenever a claw or a limb is cut off, the corresponding cells immediately disappear. They inform the member and try to compensate for it, in addition, as soon as the process of renewing the missing member is finished, the productive cells stop working and it is as if they automatically understand when it is time to end the work. They have arrived; if you cut one of the sponge animals that lives in fresh water in half, each half will complete itself and become a complete person, the head of a red earthworm. take it away, it will make another head for itself." (Ibid.: 68-64) He also mentions examples of mysterious guidance in animals

in the book of Tawheed, which is called instinct... and whether such actions in animals It is ruled out if it is through teaching and learning, because in some creatures, things are done if they do not see their past and future generations. Then he quotes from the book "The Secret of Creation" that:

They call an insect called "Ammophile", which they say is smaller than a bee and bigger than a fly... Whenever this animal lays eggs, it is a worm that eats that worm. It finds a river and sits on the worm's back and lumbar vertebra, then it stings like an ampoule at a certain point on its back, but it is very precise that it doesn't sting too much, it stings less. As much as this animal becomes numb, it falls but does not die. Because if he dies, he bites and his purpose is not achieved, he bites so that he is naked and does not move. Then it lays eggs there and dies immediately after laying eggs. Then her eggs are born, they feed on the body of the same worm until they grow up, find feathers and then live a normal life. When he arrives, he repeats exactly the same thing as the mother, that is, he goes and finds the same insect, injects it in the exact sensitive spot that he injected, and then the same thing. The action is repeated. They say how can this be justified through teaching and learning?

4.5. The final evaluation of professor Motahari through sensory and scientific study

Professor Motahari does not consider reasoning through order or through guidance sufficient to prove the existence of God. and assigns limited effectiveness to them. And contrary to what he stated in the book Causes of Tendency to Materialism, in the footnotes of the book Principles of Philosophy and Method of Realism, he does not consider these two types of arguments as rational arguments, because he believes that they do not meet the conditions of a philosophical argument. "The way of sensory and scientific study of creation is the best way in terms of its simplicity, clarity and generality. Using this way does not require a clear heart and high emotions, nor a single, reasoning and mature intellect familiar with the principles of proof. But this The path only takes us to the first place and that's enough. That is, it makes us understand that nature is subject to a supernatural power, and of course, this is not enough to know God." Then, in explaining this matter, he says: Studying the works of creation is the maximum that makes us believe in the existence of the power of the poet, scholar, sage, and manager who turns and governs nature. But is that God's power, that is, it is obligatory and not self-born and created by someone else? Sensory sciences and human natural experiences are incapable of denying and proving this matter... In addition, we have seen in the past that the implication of the two reasons of order and guidance, although it creates discontinuities and dogmas, logically does not allow the possibility of accidents and incidents. - It can negate even if its probability is one unit of a number that will never fit into our illusion.

Professor Motahari does not consider reasoning through sensory and scientific study to be a philosophical argument because he believes that it does not meet the conditions of a philosophical argument; Therefore, he says: According to philosophers, it is necessary for a preliminary argument to be necessary, permanent and general. Philosophical and mathematical proofs are based on preliminaries that cannot be found in the mathematical calculation of probabilities. It is worth noting that the Holy Qur'an calls works and creations as "verses" and the attention that is found in this way is called "tezker" and reminder. The Holy Quran wants to make the study of creatures a means of punishment and awakening of nature. That is, the Qur'an has made the study of creatures a confirmation for the path of nature and heart. The purpose of pushing to study in creatures is punishment and remembrance, not reasoning and inference." (Motahari, Principles of Philosophy and Realism Method, Vol. 5, pp. 71-70)

As it can be deduced from the above statement, Professor Motahari clearly considers reasoning through sensory and scientific methods to be irrational, and he believes that such a method alone cannot prove the God desired by religious people. It seems that here Professor Motahari comes very close to Hume's view on the argument of order. and provides a similar assessment.

5. Hume's interpretation based on the intrinsic guidance of reason for order

As it has been shown, the majority of Hume's problems are based on the explanation based on the allegory of order, not on any kind of explanation of the argument of order. In general philosophy, Dr. Mojtaboi brings Hume's expression of the proof of order, that the way of guiding beings, which was expressed by Professor Motahari, is very similar to Hume's expression of order. Hume said:

... But regardless of the objections raised in this matter, I admit that there are other components of the universe (besides the machines of human invention) that closely resemble the structure of the universe, and therefore a better guess about It provides the global origin of this system. These parts are animals and plants. It is obvious that the universe is more like an animal or a plant than a clock or a loom. Therefore, its cause is most likely similar to the first cause. (Quoted by Popkin and Stroll with translation by Mojtbavi, 1368: 218)

Dr. Mojtbavi says about the inherent order and inner guidance of beings:

... This is the originality of the life force, a force that regulates itself and has a purpose... In living beings, guidance towards survival is important, and this is the attention and movement towards the goal. This guidance is not imposed from outside. ... Nature itself maintains this

balance and evolution from within itself, that is, it has an automatic device within itself that compensates for deficiencies. For example, in order to survive, the organism must maintain the number of blood cells. Now, if the environment changes, if the creature is only affected, like a machine that is completely subject to its environment, it will not react in the direction of its survival and evolution. If the car is left in a humid environment, it rusts, that is, the nature of the car does not act to resist rust. But as soon as a living being is placed in an environment that is damaged, it starts to resist and strengthen itself. For example, when he goes to a high place, he increases his red blood cells so that enough oxygen reaches the body. When he is attacked by an infectious disease, he starts making white blood cells so that the body can defend itself. slow or if exposed to strong sunlight, a curtain is found on the skin of the body to prevent the sun's rays from penetrating under the skin and passing through the cells and tissues, or if dealing with iron For example, the skin of the hand becomes thick and many other examples. These cannot be justified by random changes, but we must say that there is an active force inside this being and this force is automatically adjusted in the direction of survival and reaching the goal.

In his second form, Hume stated what is wrong with attributing the visible order in the world to the essence of matter and not to the regulator outside of their essence. Matter may have a source or origin of order in its essence, order resulting from an unknown internal cause may lead to the highest type of order. But according to the mentioned explanations, it can be said that the inherent order and finality of matter can also be compatible with the existence of a wise and resourceful creator. In other words, it can be claimed that the movement towards the goal that exists within every creature is hidden in them by a wise and resourceful creator. Therefore, it cannot be logically certain and certain. Because the possibility of the inherent order being random is still not ruled out. Therefore, although from a philosophical point of view, its certainty is not certain, but it increases the probability of non-randomness of the inherent order of beings. Therefore, while presenting his criticisms, Hume acknowledges that the proof of order, although it is not a valid philosophical proof, can be a proof of the existence of a capable and purposeful regulator of the world. But Hume's criticisms express the important point that the teleological argument confirms only a part of the elements of theism and is completely ambiguous in relation to other parts. In other words, the fact that the world is made with planning and purposefulness is only a part of the elements of theism, and it does not help the believers in any way compared to other elements of theism. Because belief in God consists of the sum of the following propositions:

"(1) The world has been purposefully designed.

(2) The world was designed by exactly one person.

- (3) The world was created out of nothingness.
- (4) The world was created by the person who designed it.
- (5) The creator of the universe is absolute, omnipotent and omniscient.
- (6) The creator of the universe is an eternal spirit without a body and is not dependent on natural objects in any way. The teleological argument may give us a little evidence for (1), but it does nothing at all for propositions (2) through (6)." (For more, see Plantinga, *God, Freedom, and Evil*, Translation by Saeedi Mehr) Therefore, according to the above explanations, it becomes clear that reasoning through order has a limited efficiency and is not able to prove the God desired by religious people; although it can be a good proof for the existence of God, whose existence is many times more likely than It is the absence of it.

Hume's studies in the philosophy of religion aim at evaluating the reasons for the correctness of religious beliefs and investigating the causes of the phenomenon called religion in history and society. In order to do these two tasks, he used a single research method in most cases, and called it "experimental reasoning" or "causal inference". The reason for Hume's use of this method is his belief in experience. He believes that judgment about all factual matters, including the components of religious belief, such as belief in the existence of God or the occurrence of miracles, should be done by the method of causal inference. The issues that Hume examined in the philosophy of religion, on the one hand, are influenced by this methodological point of view, and on the other hand, they are due to the special historical situation of his time. Because in Hume's time, natural or rational religion and especially specific topics such as: the proof of order and the proof of miracles, have been the attention of thinkers. Based on this, Hume has prioritized such topics in his research in the field of philosophy of religion.

David Hume (1776-1711), a Scottish philosopher of the 18th century, is one of the pioneers of new philosophy. He has written in various fields. Some consider him a historian because of his historical works, and some consider him an epistemologist, and if we consider the volume of his writings about religion, we should also consider him a philosopher of religion. According to some historians specializing in Hume's philosophical thought, his writings on religion are more than his writings on any other subject (except history) (Gaskin, 1988, p. 1). Hume's entire philosophy of religion is a discussion of the relationship between reason and religious belief. His writings in the field of the philosophy of religion, each of them deals with a rational discussion about religion. These writings can be divided and classified in different ways. In a general division, some of these writings are related to the proofs of confirming and proving the correctness of religion and religious belief, and a smaller part of

these writings deal with the cause of a phenomenon called religious belief. In Nazer's writings, two general types can be distinguished: a group of these writings discuss about rational or natural religion (2) and examine the proofs that philosophers and theologians They have put forward the title of intellectual proofs (as opposed to narrative and historical proofs) of the existence of God; Another group deals with the criticism and examination of the historical evidence and correctness of religious belief. The historical evidence criticized by Hume is the miracles that are mentioned in historical texts and holy texts as confirmation and proof of religious beliefs. In this way, referring to the occurrence of miracles to prove religious beliefs is also a rational reason, because it is based on this general argument: "A miracle is something that cannot happen without the intervention of a supernatural and divine power, but it happened, so it is divine." There is one who made the miracle come true. Therefore, the purpose of dividing the evidence into intellectual and historical is not to exclude the reason of miracles from the domain of reason. But since the supporters of revelation-based theology (revelation religion(3)) sometimes benefit from the reason of miracles as a prelude to the teachings of revelation, from this point of view, it is possible to criticize the reason (based on miracles) In a sense, criticism of religion was considered a revelation. In this way, Hume's works about religion are divided into three groups (4), all of which are written from a critical perspective and in opposition to religious belief. These three groups are as follows:

- 1) Criticism of rational evidences for proving God, or criticism of rational religion or, in Hume's own interpretation, natural religion;
- 2) Criticism of the proofs of the correctness of the Christian revelation and the reliability of the Holy Book, or criticism of the religion of religion or revealed religion;
- 3) Finding the cause of the emergence of religious belief in human history or discovering the psychological, social and historical causes of religion.

Perhaps another group can be added to these three groups, in which some teachings of religious ethics and the effects of religion on morality have been examined and criticized. Hume followed a single methodology in all his criticisms related to these three or four groups. In his opinion, the correct way to know the facts is to search and identify the causal relationships between the phenomena, provided that we have a correct analysis and understanding of the cause and effect relationship and know the validity and proficiency of judgments based on the correct research method. In order to have a correct understanding of the position of Hume's philosophy of religion, we must know the common questions and thoughts of his time. It seems that if we examine the two issues of "methodology" and

"different approaches to the discussion of reason and religion" in his time and their background, we will be able to find out the position of his works correctly and his intentions in choosing the subject and Let's identify the discussion method.

Methodology

Hume's methodological background

One of the most important events of the new period is the attention of thinkers to the problem of method. The English philosopher Francis Bacon (1626-1561) is in the forefront of those who paid special attention to the method. He writes in the new Organon (5): "With the usual methods, neither great progress in scientific opinions is achieved, nor scientific works worthy of attention are obtained" (Jahangiri, 1369, p. 127). By common methods, Bacon means the methods derived from Aristotelian logic which were prevalent in his time. According to Bacon, common sciences in his time are not useful in discovering new industries, and the logic of his time does not help to discover new sciences (Jahangiri, *ibid.*, p. 14). Bacon was of the opinion that analogical reasoning does not provide new material and does not teach new knowledge, but only proves the truth that is implied in the introduction of the Kabri, and moreover, it deals with words and not with objects. And it is based on the assumptions accepted by Aristotle and his followers, and it was made without careful observation and experience of the details (*ibid.*). This critical look at the method of the predecessors and special attention to the problem of the method was not reserved for Bacon. People like Descartes (1650-1596 AD), Galileo (1642-1564 AD) and Newton (1727-1642 AD) also paid special attention to this issue. In the new era, "many books written about the scientific method, regardless of whether the supporter of the method They were experimental (such as Bacon's method) or mathematical method (such as Descartes' method) or a combination of both (such as Galileo's and Newton's method), they were common in the sense that they all mistrust and benefit from generalizations. And they showed hastily about nature" (Boomer, 1978, p. 329). These general and hasty generalizations were based on the assumption that with a few observations, one can know the essence and essence of things, and by knowing these unchanging essences, one can identify all the effects of things. According to the new thinkers, these entities are hidden things that can never be recognized and acknowledged, and one should ignore the achievement and knowledge of them and rely on the observation of obvious things. In this chapter, Newton says: "Modern authors, leaving aside the discussion of ideals and intrinsic forms and hidden qualities, have tried to study the phenomena of nature according to the laws of mathematics... The main task of natural philosophy is to make false assumptions, reason based on phenomena and infer causes from effects" (*ibid.*, p. 410); Therefore, if we sometimes come across words like face in the interpretations of new

philosophers, we should not understand and receive the same Aristotelian meaning from them. In some cases, Bacon mentions images with the name of laws. For example, in the second book of *Organon Nou*, he wrote: "When I speak of images, I mean nothing but those laws and determinations of pure reality that maintain and create each of the simple natures, such as heat, light, weight in any type of material and subject that is susceptible and capable of them; Therefore, the form of heat or the form of light is the same as the law of heat or the law of light" (Lazy, 1972 and 1980, p. 77). Newton also did not seek to achieve the forms of objects from scientific research, but rather wanted to discover the laws of nature and in this work, he turns to experience and observation. He himself says: "In my opinion, principles and principles such as gravity are not mysterious and latent qualities that arise from the specific forms of objects (6), but they are the general laws of nature by which objects themselves are formed. they become; The reality and correctness of those principles are revealed to us through phenomena, even though their causes have not yet been discovered; Because these principles are obvious qualities and only their causes are hidden. Aristotelians did not use the title of latent qualities in the case of visible qualities, but in the case of qualities that they thought were hidden in objects and considered them to be the unknown causes of obvious effects. Saying that every type of object has a special hidden and mysterious quality through which it acts and reveals its effects, means not saying anything;

But deducing one or two general principles of motion from seeing the phenomena and then showing how the qualities and actions of all material objects arise from these obvious principles, will be like taking a big step in philosophy. A scholar was governed and guided by laws. These laws were discovered through observation and experience, and the new issue that he raised for scientists was that "we are a part of nature, so to a large extent we must be governed and guided by such laws; As a result, a tension arose between our perception of ourselves as moral and rational beings on the one hand and new science on the other hand, and took root during the century and is still with us." Hume wanted this tension by applying Newton's scientific method in the realm of human sciences to solve He was the follower of Newton's scientific method. In this regard, some historians of science believe that "Hume's conception of the scientific method that he himself followed and explained clearly was taken from Newton" (Capaldi, (?), p. 250). Hume sought to apply the advice of the pioneers of the new age and avoid clinging to hidden characteristics such as physical forms for scientific explanation and pay attention to observation in his research. In this way, he realized the negative aspect of this recommendation by suggesting the sterility of previous judgments in the development of our knowledge about real affairs and also by pushing back the analogical method from the realm of real affairs, and by turning to the experimental method, he realized the positive aspect of the aforementioned recommendation. followed. Hume agreed with

Newton in rejecting the hypotheses. Newton rejected the hypothesis in a certain sense. What he meant by hypothesis was anything that is not derived from perceptible phenomena. From his point of view, assumptions whether physical or metaphysical, whether indicative of hidden principles or mechanical attributes, have no place in empirical philosophy (Burt, (?), p. 215). He spoke clearly about the rejection of hypotheses: "My opinion is that a person should also avoid giving importance to hypotheses just as he avoids fallacies" (ibid., p. 212). He said that there is no trust in assumptions, "the right way to investigate the properties of things is to discover these properties through experience" (ibid., p. 213) and like "the moderns, by abandoning material forms and hidden principles... subordinated the phenomena of nature." Let's put mathematical rules" (ibid., p. 211). Hume, like Newton, did not insist on hidden attributes and material forms to explain the events and considered this act as an insolent and fruitless hypothesizing, through which the ancients failed to achieve true knowledge (Hume, 1738, introduction) and on the other hand, the modernists achieved success by turning away from it. Hume considers the method that researches based on the abstract principles of the past and derives numerous results based on those principles to be ineffective. He knows and believes that just as this method has been abolished in natural philosophy and the main reliance has been placed on evidence derived from experience, the same should be done in the human sciences and avoid resorting to previous principles and rely on experience. Hume's prominence in this field can be seen in two parts: first, his revised and simple explanation of the necessity of observing and experimenting, and second, his effort to apply the experimental method in the field of human affairs. This recent work of his - as we mentioned before - can be considered as an attempt to solve the problem that has arisen in the new science, based on the fact that, on the one hand, man is a part of nature and should be the subject and place of the laws that govern it, and from On the other hand, he is a rational and moral being and has special aspects, so how can we judge him according to the method of modern scholars? In the following, we will discuss the scientific method approved by Hume and describe his interpretation of the experimental method. do

2. Experimental reasoning or correct method of knowledge

Experimental reasoning or the method based on causal inference is the same method that enabled the new scientists of Hume's time to develop knowledge and dominate nature, and now Hume, by explaining this method, tried to pave the way for the application of the experimental reasoning method in the realm of human sciences. And in this way, he put human philosophy on a new foundation, just as Newton revolutionized natural philosophy and founded it on a new foundation. Hume says in his treatise: "In judging the actions of humans, we must follow the same rules of reasoning about foreign nobles.

Experimental argument is the causal inference that Hume asks in the position of explanation: "What is the nature of our arguments about real matters?" And then he himself says in response: "Arguments related to real matters are based on the relationship between cause and effect." And he asks again: "What is the basis of the arguments related to the causal relationship?" And he answers with emphasis: "Experience".

Hume's explanation of this method is based on one of the two dogmatic rules of empiricism - according to Quine's interpretation (7) - which, ironically, one of the prominent rationalists in the history of new rationalism, Leibniz (8) (1716-1646) proposed and later Hume paid special attention to it (9). In this ruling, cases are divided into two analytical and composite groups. Analytical theorems have the advantage that they are always logically valid, but they have the shortcoming of not being able to develop our knowledge. But compound theorems of relationships between real things bring us new news and expand our knowledge, although their truth is probable and they never reach the rank of logical certainty; That is, they are not such that their negation leads us to contradiction. The contradiction of any true compound theorem can be imagined, without requiring a contradiction.

Of course, Hume does not use analytical and synthetic interpretations, as Leibniz used other interpretations before him. Analytical and composite interpretations are those of Kant (1804-1724), which is a well-known term today. Leibniz interpreted analytical theorems as rational truths, reasoning truths or rational truths, and called compound theorems real truths or real truths (Leibnitz, 1714, p. 123). Hume considered analytic theorems to express the relationship between ideas and compound theorems to express the relationships between real things. Leaving aside the difference in terms, Hume based on such a division of propositions, was of the opinion that "all our arguments can be considered in two types: "probative argument" or argument that is related to the relationships between concepts and "probabilistic argument" or An argument that is related to matters of fact and existence" (Hume, 1748-1751, p. 35).

The research method related to probabilistic reasoning is the experimental method or causal inference that Hume recommended for the development of knowledge, and he knew the way to discover unknowns based on past information, and he believed that the causal relationship is only a relationship [and reasoning Ali is the only argument] that "can go beyond the senses and make us aware of beings and objects that we do not see or feel.

In this method, observation plays the main role and one should never hope to think about the meaning of words and images. This pioneering observation seeks to discover causal relationships between real phenomena. Causal relationships are such that they can never be discovered without observation. It is never possible to predict its effect from thinking about

the meaning of a particular cause. Only if we leave ourselves in the hands of experience, we can identify the causal relationships, and in this way, whenever we become aware of the existence of a cause, we can guess the occurrence of its effect, and in this guess, we can reach a knowledge lower than logical certainty. Some of this knowledge is reliable and acceptable. Now the question is raised that what is the causal relationship that cannot be understood without observation? The answer to this question is explained by Hume's theory of causality.

Causality according to Hume

According to his experience, Hume believes that an impression must be searched for the concept of causality, otherwise the concept of causality will be an illusion, just like the concept of essence; Therefore, he first looks for an impression in specific causes and does not find a common thing in all the things we call causes to consider it as the source of the concept of causality; Therefore, it comes to the conclusion that the notion of causality must be caused by a relationship between things (Hume, 1738-40, p. 123). He has considered several ratios, which he has included in his definitions of causality in the first research (research on human understanding) (10).

In one of the definitions he provides for causality, he mentioned the sequence ratio, which is something that can be observed and experienced and can be returned to a certain impression. The aforementioned definition is as follows: "The cause is an object that is followed by another object, if all objects similar to the first object are followed by objects similar to the second object" (ibid., p. 60).

Immediately after this definition, Hume gives another definition that does not agree much with his sensuous view. The aforementioned definition says: "[The cause of something that something else follows] is that if the first thing were not, the second thing would never exist" (ibid.). In this definition, the necessary relationship between the first and second thing, that is, cause and effect, is assumed; However, it is difficult or impossible to return the idea of such a necessity to an impression. It is to resolve such ambiguity that Hume presents the third definition with an introduction. First, he says: "Whenever a cause appears, it moves our mind to the idea of the effect through a transfer from habit. We have experienced such a transfer out of habit" (ibid.) and we can, by changing the definition, present the necessity in the previous definition in such a way that it can be referred to an experience and, as a result, an impression; Therefore, "the cause is an object that is followed by another object, and its appearance always transfers thought to [the same] other object" (ibid.). In this way, Hume is of the opinion that the feeling or impression that creates the idea of causality is a familiar connection that is established in our mind between two consecutive things. Such a feeling,

according to Hume's terminology, is not a sensory impression, because in none of the times when we felt two things in succession, something called a connection or a necessary connection came to our senses, but from the repetition of this feeling. Sequence, a state arises in our mind which becomes the origin of the notion of causality as a secondary impression or - as Hume calls it - a reflective impression.

In his treatise, Hume goes through the same path in more detail; On the one hand, he wants to consider the ratio of necessity as the most important component in the concept of causality, because this ratio provides the necessary basis for inferring the cause from the effect or the effect from the cause, and on the other hand, he claims that there is nothing in things. A special feature called necessity cannot be observed empirically; Therefore, he is forced to offer an empirical explanation of how to extract the idea of the ratio of necessity from experience, and therefore, he must search among the primary and basic impressions. Of course, he finally finds out that the idea of the ratio of necessity cannot be extracted directly from the constant connection of things, but this work must be done indirectly, and in other words, it can only be directly derived from an inner impression. which is a reflexive impression [obtained the impression of necessity (Twyman, 2002, vol. 3, p. 303).

Now we can consider Hume's understanding of causality and causal relationship as completely empiricist. In this view, the causal relation that necessarily leads us from the impression or imagination of one thing to the image of another thing, does not have any real external necessity or, in a more precise expression, it does not know of any external necessity. rather, it is a necessity that is imposed on our mind from the repeated observation of the sequence and permanent connection of two things. Whether we want it or not, in the field of action, we attribute this mental and inner necessity to the outside and basically, without this work, life becomes impossible for us. Nature has forced us to know the world in such a way that there is a necessary relationship between real objects called causality, but despite this natural determinism, we can never find the existence of such a necessity outside of science. ; That is, we cannot find this necessity in the theoretical field.

This mental necessity is theoretically transferable to the world outside the mind in such a way that we can consider the existence of repeated sequences of two things as proof of the permanence and immutability of this sequence; But since it is always possible to imagine a state in which this sequence does not occur, no contradiction comes from denying a necessary causal relationship.

One may want to conclude by attaching a premise that it is impossible to imagine a state in which a particular cause is without its particular effect, and that premise is that "the future is

like the past", or "nature is always the same." ». Hume asks: Where did this introduction itself become known to you? If someone says: "The future is not like the past." Or if he says: "Nature is not always the same", has he committed a contradiction? Definitely not; Therefore, these premises cannot be proved by the previous proof method. Inevitably, to prove them, one must refer to the method of probable reasoning, that is, relying on past observations, in which case, our reasoning will be far away; That is, to prove this premise, one must rely on the premise itself.

In this way, Hume says: the same principle of nature, which is the foundation of all empirical and probable arguments, can never enter our knowledge. Nature has already equipped us with this principle; Without it, knowledge cannot be achieved and it itself is beyond our knowledge. With such a position, Hume distanced himself from his empiricism and came close to the Scottish naturalists, and that is why some considered Hume a naturalist and considered this aspect of his thought to be Kant's inspiration. are

Therefore, even though it is not possible to recognize and confirm the necessary relationship between real things, predicting future events based on past events and knowing intangible things by relying on visible things is possible only by assuming such a relationship. . This assumption is actually the extension of mental necessity to the outside, which if done with awareness and insight, does not make us unaware of the suspicion of our conclusions.

With the above explanations, it becomes clear that the research method approved by Hume is the identification and investigation of causal relationships between objects, and this is not possible without observation; It also becomes clear that one can never gain knowledge about real things without observation, because firstly, about real things, we cannot rely on the proof method, which is a previous method, and secondly, if we want, on the experimental method. (Discovering causal relationships) We have no choice but to observe and experience. From here, we can understand why in order to progress in moral philosophy or in its modern interpretation, human sciences, first of all, the method of studying knowledge in the realm of these sciences must be revised and man, despite having special dimensions, is a part of nature. He counted it and considered it as a subject for empirical research and decided that man and the conditions related to him are a part of real affairs; Therefore, it is not possible to judge him by the previous proof method. Secondly, after denying the application of analogical method in the field of human sciences, he identified and applied the alternative method; That is, the method of experimental reasoning, which is a method based and documented on the causal relationship, which itself is a relationship that can be identified and examined exclusively through observation and experience.

Two approaches to the philosophy of religion in Hume's time: faithism and rationalism

Background:

The history of the Christian word - perhaps in all its periods - has reported the presence of two approaches to the problem of the relationship between reason and religion: the approach of rationalism and the approach of faith. In 1277, Etienne Tempier, the bishop of the Parish Church, at the request of the Pope, provided a list of beliefs that he and the Catholic Church considered anti-religious beliefs. This list consisted of 219 cases. Some of those cases, such as "Qadam Alam", "God's lack of knowledge of details" and "the imperishability of human souls", are reminiscent of Ghazali's opinion, who, in his rejection of philosophers, called twenty of their beliefs false and sometimes blasphemous. There is an interesting theorem in Tempier's list, that is, "One should only believe in something that is self-evident or deduced from self-evident theorems" (Reck: Gilson, (?), pp. 58-59). Considering such an opinion as blasphemous can be considered as a decisive vote on the issue of the relationship between science and faith. In the new philosophy, John Locke (16) (1704-1632), an English philosopher, formed this position to confront the sectarians of his time, and later Clifford (17) (1879-1845), a mathematician and philosopher. English used it to fight against religious beliefs; But as it can be seen and we also saw in the list of Tempier's rulings, this view is not specific to the new era of philosophical thought, just as the view opposite to it, which is famous in our time with faithism, has also had supporters for a long time.

Tempier's intention of opposing the position of relativism was to condemn the Latin Ibn Rushdians in the 13th century, which is a group belonging to the Middle Ages; But the discussion of the relationship between reason and religion is an old dispute, and the believers in relativism and faithism both have an older history than this. Tertullian (155-240), who was one of the famous fathers of the church, has famous statements against Greek rationalism. including the famous saying "What to do with Athens and Jerusalem?" Or, in a thought-provoking speech, in the position of emphasizing and strengthening his faith, he says: "I am sure of it because it is impossible. There have been debates about agreeing or opposing relativism from the time of the church fathers until the time when Locke's view of relativism It is proof of the fact that the issue of reason and religion or reason and faith has always been the subject of the history of the words of Christians in the West. This concern or the constant problem of Western philosophers and theologians has a prominent face in the Middle Ages (20) and while this discussion flourished in different periods of the Middle Ages or the Christian era, the dominance of Christianity during this period caused it. That the source of certainty for the man of that age is divine revelation, and from this passage, a kind of comforting imagination prevails over the man of that time. In the period that is called

renaissance and events such as the religious reform movement parallel to it have occurred, this imaginary ease is breached and for the first time the anchor of this stability and stability is shaken. This anchorage is the origin of human certainty in the Christian era, that is, the Bible. Of course, the religious reform movement did not question the authority of this factor of stability, but cast doubt on the dominant and popular interpretation of the Bible. According to Martin Luther (1546-1483), Christians do not need an intermediary called the church to understand divine revelation; They can directly understand the divine message. One of the articles of his ninety-five-point declaration (1517 AD) in opposition to the Catholic Church is as follows: "The Bible is the only source of Christian faith." Despite such an article, we do not doubt that Luther undoubtedly believed in the authority of the Bible, but he also believed that "the only governing power that is absolute among Christians is the Bible." It has been said that the Bible should be made "understandable to the masses of believers so that they can understand it correctly from the grace of the Holy Spirit and through the faith of the heart." (Nass, (?), p. 450); In other words, in Luther's opinion, the understanding of the Bible should not be tied to the understanding of the Lord of the Church and the interpretation of the holy text is within the power of understanding and knowledge of everyone. In this way, despite his faith, Luther, through the prescription and provision of pluralism In the interpretations of the Holy Bible, it provided the ground for feeling the need of an authority to judge between multiple opinions and facilitated the reference to reason and putting aside the authority of the Bible. Some works in the realm of rational or natural theology that appeared in the second half of the 16th century can be evidence of the importance of referring to reason among the theologians of that time. Montaigne (1592-1533) in 1568 translated the book of the author of reason. Spanish-oriented, Raymond Seaband. This book deals with natural theology. But later, Montaigne observes that even by accepting the authority of reason, it is not possible to put an end to the difference of opinions, and as a result, he considers the plurality of opinions in the realm of philosophy, theology and science as a justification for defending skepticism. The subject of the relationship between reason and religion has always been the focus of philosophers. The founders of the new philosophy, such as Bacon and Descartes, thought that if they separated the realm of reason and faith, they could avoid its conflict with religion while fulfilling the right of reason, and in this way, benefit from turning to thinking. They should benefit rationally, without being caught in the danger of conflict with religion. Bacon says: "If we are inclined to investigate sacred theology, then we must leave the small boat of human reason and board the ship of the church, which alone has a divine compass to find the right path" (Boomer , 1978, p. 332). Descartes also considers it necessary to submit to divine revelation in matters related to God and says: If God reveals things about himself, such as the mystery of the incarnation and the Trinity, that is beyond the natural power of our intellect. Yes, we should accept without thinking, even if we cannot understand them clearly; Because

the existence of things beyond our understanding in the greatness of God and also in His creations should not be considered strange.

Of course, apart from separating the realms of reason and faith, Descartes resorted to another way to resolve the conflict between reason and religion. He believes that by relying on the certainty of knowledge derived from divine revelation, we should put aside our natural knowledge in cases that are contrary to divine revelation and accept God's word. Descartes says in his book *Principles of Philosophy*: We must prefer divine authority and authority over our perceptions, and this is in matters where both our intellect and divine revelation have a say. Otherwise, we should not acknowledge something that we do not clearly understand. Whatever God has revealed is more certain than other things, and we must submit to God's authority and not to our own judgment, even though the natural light of reason presents us with something with the highest clarity and evidence that is against God's word. However, in cases where the evidence of God has not revealed something to us, it is not permissible for a philosopher to consider something as truth that he has not investigated.

Therefore, in cases of conflict, Descartes considers revelation to be the final arbiter, and when reason and revelation are not compatible, he mistakes reason to put revelation on the throne; But this does not mean that reason is unimportant; Because there are not many cases where such a conflict occurs, and perhaps the most important reason for the lack of conflict cases is that the revelation does not have a say in many subjects, so that it narrows the space for the intellect, and because there is such a wide space for the activity of the intellect. The correct method of guiding the intellect is very important for obtaining certain knowledge, and for this reason, Descartes pays special attention to the problem of method, and with his emphasis on the ability of the intellect to acquire knowledge, he is the founder of rationalism. It becomes purer, which was later presented and formulated by Lacquer.

Locke's relativism

In the new period, John Locke is a prominent philosopher who forms a theory about the relationship between reason and religion, which is called relativism today. Locke has an article in the nineteenth chapter of the fourth book in the book *"Inquiry about the understanding of human nature"* that can be considered as the mission statement of relativity; He says there: "... in my opinion, there is an accurate indication of whether someone is a real lover of the truth or not; And that is not to accept any case with more certainty than what its evidence warrants. It is clear that anyone who transgresses this criterion does not seek the truth for the sake of the truth and is not seeking the truth for the sake of the truth, but is looking for another goal; Because the certainty of the truth of any theorem (except self-

evident theorems) is solely dependent on the evidence that we have in favor of it, and if the confirmation of a theorem is more than the order of the corresponding theorem, it is clear that this overconfidence is caused by its other attachments, not from love for the truth.

This position of Locke is actually the continuation of the efforts of new philosophers to get out of the crisis of human opinions and ideas. Following the doubts of the likes of Luther, Erasmus (1466-1536) and Montaigne, arranging the limits of reason and clarifying its place had been the focus of new philosophers, and Locke, in the continuation of these efforts, placed reason in such a high position. It gives a re-emphasis on the importance of the role of reason in avoiding human beings from falling into the trap of superstitions; As the title of the 19th chapter of the 4th book of *Essay on Human Understanding*, i.e. the chapter "Extreme Passion", is proof of this motive.

According to Locke, reason is the main criterion for determining one's limits in relation to revelation. According to him, as he explains in the 18th chapter of the 4th book of an inquiry about human understanding, revelation is of two types; Original Revelation and Narrative Revelation: "The original revelation is the first impression that God directly creates in the mind of a person, and we cannot put a limit on it; What I mean by narrative revelation is those impressions that are transmitted to others in the form of words and conventional ways of mutual communication of ideas.

With this division, Locke wants to know in detail the role of reason regarding revelation. From his point of view, even in the position of directly receiving revelation from God, a person who perceives cannot accept something that is incompatible with the self-evident principles of reason, and this inability is caused by the judgment of reason, which obliges a person to accept. He should refrain from the impossible and contradicting the self-evident principles of reason. Locke's argument is that if we are allowed to accept something that is inconsistent with the self-evident principles of reason, "we are always exposed to the problem that we do not understand how something can be done by God, the only open-handed creator." We think that, if he is considered truthful, he will inevitably overturn all the principles and foundations of science, which he himself has bestowed upon us, and will destroy all our powers, the highest part of his artefacts. That is, it will completely destroy our understandings and will put a person in a situation where his share of the light of guidance will be less than the share of dead and animals who do not have life after death. (ibid., pp. 11-12).

When the intellect has such authority in front of the original revelation, it is clear that it acts more authoritatively in front of the imitation revelation; Because the revelation that has

reached us through the transmission of others has less benefit of reassurance; This is because, firstly, our confidence in issuing this revelation report from the Prophet or the interpreter of revelation is always subject to doubt; That is, we give the possibility of not issuing this word from the recipient of the revelation; Secondly, our understanding of his words and reports is always subject to the possibility of error and misunderstanding; Therefore, reason forbids us from accepting any theory that is incompatible with the obvious and certain principles of reason, even if it is stated in a text that it is claimed to be revealed. In this way, reason finds absolute rule and one must ask What will be the position of revelation or faith? According to Locke, "every case that has been revealed and our mind, with the help of its natural powers and imaginations, cannot judge its truth, is exclusively a matter of faith and devotion and beyond reason" (ibid., p. 15).

Locke accepts faith only where reason cannot issue a verdict. This inability may be due to the fact that some of the concepts used in a case are beyond the limits of our natural powers, and it may be due to the fact that we have doubts about a case, even though it is not fundamentally unreasonable. Or let us remain suspicious. In these two assumptions, faith should be resorted to (same); But where reason has a ruling that is contrary to faith, it is preferable to the ruling of reason, and recourse to faith is prohibited.

By adopting such a position, the room for faith becomes small; Because what Locke means by the word faith is the same thing that was understood by faith in the Middle Ages. In the Middle Ages, having faith meant accepting something because God had revealed it; And having knowledge means accepting something that we consider to be true in the light of the natural light of reason (Gilson, (?), p. 64). Despite such similarities in the use of the word faith and science between Locke and medieval people such as Thomas Aquinas, Locke's approach regarding the relationship between science and faith or reason and religion is clearly different from their approach. According to the medieval thinkers, "faith, according to its definition, is necessary for the intellect to accept something that it considers to be the main contradiction of the basic principles of the intellect or one of its necessary accessories" (ibid., p. 65). Locke's view is in direct contrast. Locke never accepts things that are contrary to the self-evident principles of reason. In this way, Locke is one of the heralds of rationalism in the matter of religion, and that is why the range of recourse to faith, in the sense he intended, is threatened by reason and is much smaller than the range intended by the medievals and It will be Descartes. Locke's general understanding of the place of reason in the realm of ethics of belief requires that belief in the existence of God is acceptable only when it is confirmed by reason. In the 10th chapter of his book *An Inquiry into the Understanding of Humanity*, Locke deals with the same subject and clearly says that we can gain knowledge about the existence of God, and continues to prove the existence of God. According to him, we can find

certain knowledge about God's existence, and this knowledge is obtained by referring to our natural powers.

The development of natural theology, the consequence of relativism

This way of looking at the problem of reason and faith and the influence of reason in theological issues has been the inspiration of a wide movement called natural theology in the 17th and 18th centuries. Many writers have written on this subject and have tried to establish rational arguments for the existence of God and other religious beliefs, and even in this way they have benefited from the findings and methods of modern sciences that occurred during the scientific revolution. One of the most attractive topics raised in the works of these philosophers was the question of the existence of God. In his new research on human understanding, Leibniz says: "I believe that almost all the methods used to prove the existence of God are valid and can achieve their goal, provided that they are presented in a complete way." (Jolly, 1995, p. 253). Such a decisive and all-encompassing opinion - in the interest of contradiction - is reminiscent of William Acme's decisive opinion in the opposite direction, which "was of the opinion that absolutely nothing can be proved about God in the light of evolutionary reason, even the existence of God" (Gilson), p. 76). Unlike Achemy, the scholars of the 17th and 18th centuries were more interested in the application of reason in the subject of theology than in closing reason about it. A famous writer like Samuel Clarke (1729-1675) (25) in the early years of the 18th century (1704-5) gave two series of lectures, which were later titled Discourses on the Existence and Attributes of God, the Requirements of Natural (Rational) Religion, and the Authenticity of Revelation. Mashi was published. In the early years of the 19th century, a famous work called Hiyat al-Tabi'i: Qara'ini ver existence va sifat al-ehi (26) was published, which received a lot of attention. This work was written by William Paley (1805-1743) (27), an English moral philosopher and theologian. In this work, Pili presented a wide-ranging interpretation of the "argument of order" or the "argument of design and planning". By dealing with the details of the comparative anatomy of the eyes, ears, muscles and bones and describing the precision and delicacy used in adjusting them to act in the best way, he tried to establish a conclusive proof or proofs for the existence of God.

This focus on reasoning and providing evidence for God's existence is the result of Lac's cultivation in the 17th century. As they said in this regard: "From Locke's book entitled The Reasonableness of Christ, which was written in 1695..., it was only one step away from the natural religion of the 18th century enlighteners" (Boomer, 1978, p. 333). This one step was taken many times by the philosophers and theologians of that time until it was Pili's turn and he also took this step again. The great emphasis on the importance of rationality in this

process limits the path of faith to insignificant areas. This current of thought considers reason as the final arbiter and leaves revelation in such strictness that revealed religion practically leaves the stage and the remaining religion becomes natural religion. That is, a religion that arose from reason and does not need revelation. This religion is so faithful to the authority of reason that it does not have any opposition with the human-centered trend of the new era. Deism is a current of thought that proves the new man's desire for self-sufficiency in reason. Lac is one of the most effective figures in the emergence of this trend. "The term deism was first used in the 16th century and about some writers, most of whom belonged to the last part of the 17th century and the beginning of the 18th century. They considered the idea of revelation and supernatural inspiration and revealed and inspired secrets to be invalid. Locke himself did not reject the concept of revelation, but insisted that reason is the judge of revelation;

; And more than anything, his motivation was to rationalize the Christian religion. Deists applied his ideas in a more extreme way and tried to turn Christianity into a purely natural religion. Their common feature was their belief in God, which distinguished them from atheists, in addition to their disbelief in a unique revelation and a supernatural plan of salvation, which was their privilege from the ancient Christians. In other words, they were intellectuals who believed in God.

In this way, it can be said that the new philosophy separated reason and religion by emphasizing rationality at the beginning of the path, and Locke further narrowed the path of faith by emphasizing that reason is the dominant authority over everything, and after Locke, everything, even religion, became a manifestation of human reason, and revealed religion was pushed aside and natural religion took its place.

Natural religion is a term that was used in the 18th century and is equivalent to the modern term of natural theology. Natural religion is a rational religion and does not rely on revelation. In contrast to the natural religion, there is a revealed religion, which is based on God's inspiration and revelation.

In response to the natural and rational religion and its difficulties, those tried to revive the revealed religion and criticize the extreme positions of the deists. In this context, a book titled *Defense of Revelation Religion* was written in 1732, that is, when Hume was twenty-one years old, and a well-known figure such as Bishop Butler (31) (1752-1692) wrote a book titled *The Analogy of Natural Religion* and He wrote a revelation with the building and the path of nature in defense of religion.

Hume's position against natural and revealed religion

So far, we have raised two important issues for understanding why and how Hume approaches certain issues in the philosophy of religion: First, we have explained why Hume gave special importance to the problem of method and also briefly with the method in question. We have come to know his confirmation in the examination of the facts, and secondly, we have found that in his time, the defense of religious belief took place in two different directions: the defense of rational religion and the defense of revealed religion. Hume has paid special attention to these two currents and has found that among all the arguments that are presented in each of these two paths, two arguments or reasons for religious belief have more grounds for methodological criticism than the rest of the arguments. First, the proof of design and order or the proof of order, which was a special concern of the defenders of the rational religion, and second, the proof of miracles, which the believers in the revealed religion benefited from. Therefore, the design and planning argument could be criticized as a methodology that sought to identify the cause of the world order, and Hume thought that the causation contained in this argument was not done in the correct way; In other words, the principles of the causal explanation method must be observed, which the proponents of the argument of design and planning have not paid attention to, and as a result, their argument is ineffective. Of course, other proofs from the arguments of the defenders of rational religion have also been noticed by Hume, but he spoke about them briefly and only limited himself to showing that these proofs basically used a wrong method to prove the existence of God. are Contrary to the proof of planning and planning, which has chosen the right method, but has not acted correctly in the application of this method. In the realm of revealed religion, the proof of miracle is the basis; The basis that proves, firstly, the existence of God and secondly, the reliability of revelation (that is, the correctness of citing a text to divine knowledge). So in this approach, everything depends on the occurrence of a miracle. The occurrence of a miracle is also a matter of real affairs, and the investigation of real affairs is not possible except by the method of causal inference. Accepting the occurrence of a miracle involves consequences in the issue of causality that are not acceptable in Hume's view, hence Hume's criticism of the miracle argument, in addition to being based on a theological or anti-religious motive, also has a methodological motive. has it.

In the following, by introducing Hume's works on the subject of philosophy of religion, we show how each of his researched subjects has a relationship with the methodological and historical contexts of his work.

Hume's works on religion

There are many researches about religion and religious claims in Hume's works. But some of his works specifically deal with religious issues. In this section, we will outline the general structure of his approach to the subject of religion and then we will state which part of this structure was provided by each of his works. In his rational examination of religion, Hume seems to answer a general question. The mentioned question is, why does a person believe in God and why does he accept the teachings of a religion? This question can be asked and answered in two ways. This question can be considered as a question about the reason for religious belief of religious people, and it can also be considered as a question about the reason of religious believers for believing in religion and religious teachings. In short, this question asks both the cause and reason of religiosity. Hume also paid attention to these two questions in various positions and tried to answer them.

In order to know the cause or causes of belief in religion, Hume wrote the book *Natural History of Religion*. In this book, he tries to study religion like any other natural phenomenon and it is known what factors cause this phenomenon. In this book, he wants to identify the causes and conditions that naturally create religion, as, for example, the cause of a phenomenon such as the rusting of iron is known. In this study, he mostly resorts to historical and psychological methods and recognizes things like fear of unknown factors or unexpected events as the cause of the phenomenon of religion.

In this section, Hume does a work similar to the work of Marx, Freud and Nietzsche. Like Hume, they have sought to provide a basis for explaining human affairs and to explain human affairs, like other natural affairs, in a scientific way. Contrary to the common view in Christianity or the method of existentialist writers, according to them, man [is not made by external factors and causes but] is the creator of his own nature, and his will and choice are effective in this direction. Freud to the psychological origin of religion and Marx to It deals with its social and economic origin and Nietzsche tries to show the origin of religion in the ethics of slavery with the genealogy of ethics.

The common denominator of all these theories - including Hume's theory - is the search for the cause of the phenomenon of religion in human history. Hume does not do this in the light of a general theory about social developments; In other words, Hume emphasizes more on the method of causal inference than on a specific hypothesis regarding the cause of the phenomenon of religion; But Marx and Freud have spoken at a time when Hume's efforts regarding the method were successful and they continued their efforts to identify a specific example as the cause of people's religious beliefs.

In the natural history of religion, in addition to historical factors and human psychological and social weaknesses, the reason for the emergence of religion is introduced, the moral effects or moral damages caused by religious belief are presented, and a comparison is made between polytheism and monotheism. and the characteristics and effects of each of them are stated. Among his other works about the cause of religious belief is an article entitled "On Superstition and Extreme Passion" which is a chapter of the book of Ethical and Political Essays. It was published in 1747. In this work, he dealt with the psychological and social origins of religious belief and listed the psychological and social harmful effects of these origins. There are more works left by Hume about the reason for religious belief. His most famous work in this regard is the book Conversations about Natural Religion. In nine of the twelve sections of this book, the proof of order is discussed and investigated. Hume refers to this argument as the posterior argument. In another part, which is the ninth part of this book, he examines a proof that he calls the previous proof, and in our times it is mostly called the cosmological proof. He has discussed this argument in the treatise on human nature and also in the research book on human understanding.

Before writing the book Conversations, he had discussed miracles in the tenth chapter of the book Research on Human Understanding. In the discussion of miracles, Hume criticizes the revealed religion. A miracle as a proof of the truthfulness of the prophets' claims is actually a proof for religious belief; The reason that leads to faith in revelation and revealed religion. In his essay "On the Immortality of the Soul", Hume opposes the belief in the immortality of man and in fact opposes one of the most important religious doctrines; And in the fifth title of the fourth chapter of the first book of the treatise, he tries to criticize the celibacy of the soul, and in this way, he criticizes the necessary foundation for considering the soul to be eternal. According to some Hume scholars, this part of the treatise could be completed with the article "On the Immortality of the Self" as the concluding section. In an article entitled "On Suicide", he tries to prove that suicide, whether There is nothing wrong with a moral or religious opinion, and in this way, he contradicts a religious ruling and, in his opinion, reveals the moral harms caused by religious perverted beliefs. In these works, Hume explicitly He discussed religious issues and in most of them he disputed the evidence of religious belief and commitment to religious beliefs and rulings. But apart from these works, he has always paid attention to the subject of religion in his other books. For example, reading the research book about human understanding shows that he is providing the necessary epistemological foundations for discussing religion; As in the final chapters of the book, it finally comes to this issue. He did not ignore the issue of religion in moral discussions, and in his research book on the principles of ethics, he recounts the harmful effects of religion in the realm of ethics.

. By looking at the mentioned works, we can clearly see that Hume designed his discussions about religion based on the application of experimental reasoning method and causal inference. When he investigates the cause of religiosity and the phenomenon of religion, he clearly sets etiology as his goal, and in fact, he considers the application of causal reasoning in the field of historical studies. In the discussion of the revealed religion, he puts the occurrence of miracles as a phenomenon reported in history as the object of research using the method of causal reasoning and casts doubt on the possibility of proving the occurrence of miracles in history and says: adherence to the rules of the method Causal inference is the unprovable requirement of knowing the occurrence of miracles in history. Hume, in the discussion of the reason or arguments for religious belief, has paid the main attention to the argument, because the defenders of this argument claim to use the method of causal inference, and Hume criticizes them for adhering to the rules of this method. He knows it is wrong and believes that even though there is no other way to prove the existence of God as a matter of fact, resorting to the method of causal inference, but the defenders of the proof of design and planning are unable to use this method in this particular issue. are

What is the relationship between causality and habit in Hume's philosophical system? Did Hume reduce causality to habit?

It cannot be said that he reduced causality to habit. Basically, his discussion about causality refers to another point, and he does not accept the reality of such a concept as the existence of a necessary and objective relationship because it cannot be observed and experienced.

When a sequence and association happens again and again and we witness this repetition, we will get used to it. Experience creates a habit of waiting in us. What we think of as a necessary relationship is our habitual awareness resulting from experience, and we mistakenly speak of the existence of a necessary relationship between A and B, or causation. For example, when we see that it rains after every thunder and lightning, we mistakenly assume that the lightning is the cause of the rain, while there is no visible causal link between them. What we observe is the "constant coexistence" of these two events, and this is different from a causal relationship.

What we experience are passive perceptions, and we have never had an unmediated experience of causal connection.

What is the place of experience and observation in Hume's philosophical system? Hume measures and explains all the concepts of his philosophical system based on what can be

observed and experienced. His goal is to adapt human thoughts to the facts of observation and experience. Hume's goal is to direct the mind of the society to all those truths that are the product of experience and forbid anything beyond that. He even mentions observation and experience about moral issues.

Why is Hume called a skeptical philosopher? Hume considers everything that is not based on observation and experience to be illusory. He believes that the analysis of many philosophical reasons to the end will empty a person of many beliefs. Therefore, he appears to be a very skeptical person. Of course, Hume himself admits that human beings cannot consider their actions and beliefs unnecessary and continue living with complete doubt. But skepticism helps people to realize that what can be proven is very small. The result of this awareness is freedom from prejudice.

Another thing to remember is that Hume had no doubts about the material world and the existence of other people. His doubt about the mental abilities of man finally leads him to the position that the existence of the material world cannot be proved through logical and rational conclusions.

Does Hume's system of thought require accepting some kind of determinism? Determinism in physics means that accurate knowledge of the current state of a system is sufficient to predict its future. With the advent of quantum physics, deterministic models were challenged.

In the first half of the 20th century, quantum theory, by discrediting the principle of causality and introducing the principle of uncertainty in its place, claimed the validity of Hume's opinion, that is, what is observed from the observation of events is only a consequence and not causality, and hence any claim It is not valid based on the causal relationship between the events. This theory claimed that causality is absolutely invalid in the world of tiny particles and in the range of events whose magnitude is characterized by the Planck number. Among other things, Heisenberg concluded the rejection of causality in his interpretation of uncertainty relations.

But it should be added that causality was later disputed in the field of uncertainty, quantum leap and Bohr's atomic model. The problem that was brought up was that the uncertainty relations are not obtained from considering the experimental facts of measurement, but are merely consequences of the fundamental assumptions of the quantum theory. Secondly, uncertainty relations are related to the epistemological field, but the discussion about the existence of causality is related to the ontological field, and because we are not able to make accurate predictions in the epistemological field, in other words, we do not have determinism in the field of epistemology. , it cannot be concluded that there is no causality in the field of

ontology either. Popper also acknowledges this point. But it is necessary to mention a quote from Carnap who said: Choice involves the general preference of one course of action over another. If the consequences of different actions cannot be predicted, how is it possible to make a choice? Even the simplest choices depend on the anticipation of possible consequences. Therefore, determinism cannot be considered completely against free will.

How do you evaluate Hume's position in the history of Western philosophy? What influence did Hume have on the philosophers after him?

Although Hume was noticed by many experts during his lifetime, including the French philosopher - Jean-Jacques Rousseau, due to his cheerfulness and genius, and in his intellectual life in his hometown of Edinburgh in the 18th century, which is known as the "Enlightenment Movement in Scotland" Yes, it was very influential, but Hume's philosophy was neglected for at least a century after him. Of course, in Germany, Kant carefully examined Hume's philosophy and, in his own words, "awakened him from his dogmatic slumber." But then it was noticed again and according to Russell, Western philosophy has not yet moved ahead of Hume in many cases. Scientists of quantum physics have taken Hume's theory of causality as a confirmation of their theory of determinism, and the representatives of the school of positivism have turned Hume's empiricism into their scientific method. Also, Hume's thoughts about "self" have been the focus of many philosophical thoughts in England. Einstein once said that if he had not read Hume's philosophy, he would not have dared to overturn Newton's physics. Hume's thought about the compatibility of "raw reality" with "theory" is of great interest today, and it can be said that it can disturb the peace of mind of any thinker.

Hume's contribution in political philosophy

Hume's influence on political philosophy can be traced through two channels. First, his emphasis is on the lack of logical connection between value issues and real issues. This logical approach was the source of inspiration and the basis of Logical Positivists to limit the scope of political philosophy discussions and exclude many of its traditional discussions. In a famous paragraph from the treatise on human nature (Hume: 1888, 469), Hume insists that the rejection of a valid argument should never be used to arrive at normative conclusions from premises related to facts and essences. This article, which is known as "Hume's Fork", has become the beginning of a wide-ranging debate under the title of "Isought problem", because it emphasizes that it is logically impossible to make value judgments (both moral and legal) that We interpret it as "must", inferred from theorems related to facts. Ought cannot be

extracted from "is". Therefore, value, moral and legal issues cannot be supported with the help of epistemological issues, and factual premises cannot lead to value and normative results. The reflection of this approach in the field of politics is that one should not recommend and prescribe political and moral principles based on research on human nature and the realities of human society, and this means the death of classical political thought, because in classical political thought, thinkers have always tried to imagine They should link the good, prosperity and right with the realities of human conditions and document the rights of people, the desired political model and the principles and values governing political relations according to their perception of human realities and human society.

Logical positivists, with a narrow and limited criterion for meaningfulness, insisted on the point that, firstly, any statements about the facts related to human beings and society must be born from experience and the experimental scientific method, because all rational and non-empirical intuitions are basically meaningless and only Meaningful theorems are theorems that can be proven experimentally. Secondly, these empirical facts about man and society cannot be used as a document of value and normative judgments in the field of politics, because the fallacy of inferring "must" from "is" dictates that logically, legal requirements and the system of rights and duties should not be based on facts and The knowledge was documented. This narrow-minded and positivist approach left only two channels for political discussions, which were the empirical study of political behaviors and the logical analysis of political concepts. Although logical positivism did not last long due to the unreasonableness of the provability thesis and their unjustified emphasis on the meaninglessness of everything that is non-experimental, Hume's logical flaw in the relationship between facts and values is still the focus of logicians and philosophers of science. In any case, the arguments of political philosophy in cases that are formed based on some facts such as human nature, need to solve the logical problem that Hume has thrown into it.

The second importance of Hume for political philosophy is related to his special perception of the issue of justice, which is evaluated as a new and different approach based on special presuppositions and claims, compared to the traditional thinking about justice. The present letter is dedicated to examining and evaluating Hume's concept of justice, and before mentioning his most important ideas in detail, I feel it necessary to provide an explanation about Hume's writings in the category of justice. His most original writing about justice is related to the treatise on human nature, which was published in 1739. it is arrived. This treatise consists of three parts or three main books. The title of the first part (Book I) is called "On Understanding", which includes Hume's epistemology and discusses the way to reach knowledge and the limitations of human knowledge and the degree of justification of human

knowledge. The second book (Book II) is about the passions, which can be called Hume's philosophy of psychology. It also discusses human will and the rationality of action.

The third book of this treatise is about the morals, which itself consists of three chapters. Its first chapter discusses virtues and vices in general, and the third chapter is dedicated to natural and non-artificial virtues. The second chapter of the third book is about justice and injustice. During this chapter, Hume discusses his most important views on justice, and by proposing an empirical theory of justice, it is clearly the view of those like John Locke and Clarke, who consider justice to be a natural thing. And they know that it has eternal and unchangeable laws and can be known by reason, it takes a distance.

The main volume of Hume's writings on the topic of justice is an attempt to answer two main questions: first, what is the origin and root of the need for justice and under what conditions are the laws of justice and the idea of justice useful, and the second question is how justice is a virtue and what is the difference or similarity Is it moral with other known virtues? A comprehensive understanding of his theory of justice can be obtained by taking a brief look at his perception of justice and comparing it with some common and famous notions of justice.

Hume's idea of justice

The dominant approach among the thinkers who are involved in the discussion of justice is that they look at justice as a virtue, value or standard that is of special value and importance independent of the desires, wills and interests of people and requires them to do what In the individual life and in the public domain and the context of society and categories such as legislation, judgment, political decision-making, distribution and allocation of resources of wealth and natural endowments, he respected the side of justice and adjusted his method, character and planning according to the principles of justice and its requirements. do According to this theory, justice, like the famous Muslim and moral cases, is ranked higher than the individual's will and interests, and he is obliged to put himself in its service, if he wants to have a reasonable and just life. Of course, thinkers defending this approach have a different analysis of the content of justice, its principles, and the way we reach the content of justice; For example, Kant, with a rationalistic approach, considers the origin of the principles of justice to be pure reason and some interpretations of the "Categorical Imperative", while John Rawls has a completely different opinion. He is of the opinion that justice and its principles have a function like the discussion of truth in the field of theoretical education, and just as the correctness of a case is known by a standard called truth, the social structure and the system of rights and desirable duties are evaluated by a standard called justice and its

principles. . According to Rawls, the principles of justice are not facts that can be discovered and understood by theoretical reason, but are the product of agreement and contract that people act on in certain situations and conditions.

Hume's conception of justice does not match this dominant approach. In his view, justice is not a value or a virtue or a measure independent of the mentality and desires of people to which they have a rational or natural obligation. Justice by itself is not even a virtue, but man needs it only in certain circumstances. The definition of justice and its content and laws is a human artifact and a product of agreement and contract that people in different societies make. So, justice is not something that we understand and tend to with the power of reason or nature and human nature, but in situations where we see ourselves in need of it and it is beneficial for us, we commit to it in the form of laws and social contracts and are motivated by it. And our motivation in complying with the laws that we have made ourselves is the benefit that is imagined by complying with them.

As it will be clear in the following discussions, Hume basically believes that where rules and regulations - which are the product of human contract and agreement - do not exist, there will be no issue to raise the issue of justice, then justice is the description of the rules and laws that the people of society In order to protect their interests, they falsify and legislate in certain circumstances. Therefore, Hume distanced himself from the idea of justice as an internal value that humans naturally and naturally desire and want to fulfill and observe. Justice is not an absolute value and virtue that is not subject to special conditions and is beneficial in all circumstances, but only in cases where people feel that they need laws to define the framework of their relationships to distribute gifts and benefits, justice becomes an issue and Its rules and laws are nothing but the agreement and contract of the members of the society. Hume is less interested in analyzing the nature of justice and is more focused on examining topics such as our internal situation in relation to justice, the conditions that provide the need for justice and fair action, and the relationship between justice and Virtues are moral. In short, it can be claimed that he answers two main questions

First, is justice a natural virtue? And secondly, what are the roots and conditions of raising the issue of justice and the need for it? The fact that Hume argues in two relatively different directions, that is, the non-virtue of justice and the conditions of justice, does not mean that he presented two theories of justice, as some people like Brian Barry think. (Barry: 1989, 148) The fact of this It is that Hume's perception of justice is based on his special preconceptions about man, the epistemic position of human action, the nature of moral virtues, and the inner motivations of man in forming society and acting to observe law and justice. Therefore, what he says in the two main axes of the roots of justice and its being

virtuous, are parts of the theory of justice that are completely consistent with the foundations and philosophical views that Hume insists on. Understanding his theory of justice is based on understanding these epistemological and philosophical foundations. Therefore, we will give a brief description of these views. Due to the fact that Hume is a scattered writer and therefore, he discusses various topics during the discussion of justice, I will try to focus only on those that are more important and help clarify and clarify his theory of justice.

The place of reason in politics and ethics

With a completely empiricist view and an anti-Aristotelian position, Hume imagines a very limited role for reason in the field of ethics and politics. Since Aristotle, rationalists have always believed that reason is the basis of moral judgments and other parts of practical wisdom such as politics. In the first part of Hume's treatise on human nature, entitled "On Understanding", which actually defines his epistemology, while presenting an analysis of human mental and epistemological abilities and capacities, Hume limits the role of reason in forming moral and political judgments, and on the contrary It opens a wide field for human feelings, desires and emotions.

His empiricist view considers a limited function for reason. Hume believes that the human mind is only capable of two tasks: judging matters of fact and understanding the relationships between ideas. What he means by real affairs is those disputes that can be resolved by referring to feelings and direct experience. Basically, intellect is the power to distinguish truth from non-truth, so in cases where there is disagreement, agreement and opposition, human intellect and wisdom are the source of dispute resolution. This difference is sometimes in real matters; That is, things can be experienced and sometimes it is about the relationships between ideas. What Hume means by "ideas" is the logical relationship between ideas. Of course, Hume's extreme empiricism allows him to limit ideas and concepts to those that are abstracted from sensory perception and experience in various ways. Therefore, according to Hume, truth and error and the judgments of reason are limited to sensory evidence or what arises from sensory perceptions.

Reason alone, as we proved earlier, can never have such effects. Morals excite inner passion and stimulate or prevent actions. Intellect by itself is unable to do this particular task. Therefore, the rules of morality cannot be the results of reason.... As long as it is true that reason has no influence on our desires and actions, it is futile to pretend that morality is discovered through rational deduction. (Hume: 1888, 458)

Now that reason does not play a role in the realm of life goals, its dignity is limited to the realm of tools and devices. Intellect is a person's helper in reaching the goals that are drawn

by another authority other than intellect. In this way, Hume deeply departs from the tradition of rationalism in practical wisdom. The tradition based on which judgments in the field of action, such as ethics and politics, owe their validity and value to reason and must be derived from rational foundations. One of the most important reasons that Hume gives in support of his anti-rationalism in the field of practical wisdom is the fallacy. The inference should be from *is*, which we mentioned briefly before.

The key point in Hume's thought is that he considers the values of the realm of practical wisdom unrelated to the objective world and related to the realm of our feelings and emotions. Therefore, it is beyond the reach of reason, which is limited to the discovery of relationships and judgment about the validity and correctness of objective and real matters. By setting aside reason as the reference and basis of ethics and politics, Hume introduces sentiment as the basis of social, political and moral life. The most central feeling that Hume mentions as the basis of social and moral life is the feeling of altruism (Sympathy) and empathy with others. Of course, there are some ambiguities in what exactly Hume means by humanity and altruism; For example, Jonathan Harrison, who is one of the most famous and accurate commentators of Hume and has written two valuable books on the analysis of Hume's epistemology and his theory of justice, states that Hume does not believe in the existence of such a thing as love for one's fellow man in human nature.

Hume writes:

In general, it can be acknowledged that there is no such tendency in human nature as love for mankind, by itself.

In any case, Hume believes that moral laws, social ends, and the principles and goals of political life are based on human feelings and emotions, and he tries to show that these emotional bases are common to a large extent in humans, so that by this means, arbitrary (Arbitrary)) to become ethics and practical wisdom. When the framework of life is drawn, then it is the turn of reason to serve as a tool and means to provide these ends. Therefore, in the final analysis, not only reason is the servant and slave of human desires and feelings, but also morality is at the service of human natural feelings and desires, because it does not sit in a higher rank to assume the role of controller of human desires, but the product and result of It is emotions, after that it is ethics and reason that must harmonize with the natural desires of human beings.

With such an analysis of reason, ethics, and social and political values, it becomes clear that Hume cannot agree with any analysis of justice that places the foundations of its principles in reason or any other reference outside human feelings and natural desires. While admitting

that we sometimes have feelings of approval and sometimes disapproval of particular cases and make such judgments based on general criteria, Hume never considers these general criteria to be rational or natural and rooted in human nature, but most of these principles are artificial. Man knows and is affected by the desires and inner feelings common to man.

The origin and motivation of seeking justice

Hume emphasizes the essential role of justice as a central political virtue. Therefore, it becomes involved in two important questions: firstly, what is the root of this virtue and why does humanity reach this point where it places justice as a basic foundation in its political and social life? And the second question is, how is justice a virtue and how is it different or similar to other moral virtues? Regarding the first question, it is important to note that Hume does not recognize a rational basis for justice, therefore, seeking justice cannot be the product of a process of theoretical inference and rational exploration. From his point of view, justice is not a rational necessity or a requirement of human wisdom. It is not the case that reason (practical human reason) without taking into account individual interests and specific conditions and situations of a person in a general and public judgment, decides on the necessity of attention to justice and the desirability of justice. If we consider the virtue of justice as a rational virtue, it will mean that the desirability and necessity of justice is absolute, permanent and unexceptionable, because the rules of practical reason, like the rules of theoretical reason, are necessary and absolute. On the other hand, Hume denies the existence of a desire and tendency and inner feeling inherent in human existence. He cannot acknowledge the meaning that human beings innately praise justice and want to respect the rights and interests of other people of their kind. Hume states that if for a reason - the explanation of which will come - the sense of duty towards justice does not arise in the person, there is no motivation inside the person to guide him towards justice. For this reason, he believes that in the "state of nature" where there is no ownership, neither justice nor injustice makes sense. This does not mean that Hume believes in the permissibility of taking each other's property in a natural state, because from his point of view, until there are no property laws, concepts such as justice and injustice, being allowed and not being allowed, are essentially irrelevant. (Ibide, 501)

According to Hume, in the state of nature, the question of why I should be just does not arise, because by definition, the state of nature refers to a state where people are not condemned by the laws of the subject. In the absence of law, there is no incentive in man to observe justice, because the question of "why should we be just" - according to Hume - is equivalent to "why should I observe laws" and because legal It does not exist, the question of why it should be observed does not arise. (Harrison: 1981, 69)

With this brief explanation, it becomes clear that Hume does not have an inner root - both rational and emotional - for justice, neither a rational obligation calls him to be just, nor does his inner feeling and love for his fellow man call him to observe the principles of justice. Rather, the root of justice should be sought in a place that justifies a person's need for the law, because as mentioned, Hume repeatedly states that when the topic of justice and injustice and the question of why I should be just is raised, a person in To live in a society where there are laws. The existence of human laws is a proof of the necessity of raising the issue of justice. In other words, the moment when people in a natural state come to the conclusion that they will put an end to this lawless situation by establishing laws, it is the moment of need for justice, and in the context of human subject laws, the category of being just - the need to obey the laws - finds meaning and meaning. . Therefore, the root of seeking justice is the same as the root of seeking the law, and the motivation for justice is the same as the motivation for the law and respect for it. The same motivation that brings humans to the point where they have to enact laws is the main motivation for justice and justifies the need to pay attention to justice.

Tying the topic of justice with human-made laws and defining justice according to laws puts Hume in front of the popular and popular definition of justice. Justice is usually defined as "giving rights to those who have rights". According to Hume, it is a clear error to consider "right" independent of justice and prior to it, then to define being just by respecting these rights and granting them to their owners. Rights have no meaning without subject laws, just as justice has no subject laws. So justice and right are both born after the formation of human laws. Therefore, there is no right independent of laws, let alone that which precedes justice. This conventional view of justice puts Hume in front of the common idea of justice from another angle. The common idea is that justice is an external criterion for judging the content of actions and behavior, for this reason, behaviors and actions are divided into two categories of just and unjust, and this external criterion is also applied to the laws themselves, and the laws are divided into two categories of just and unjust. divides But according to Hume's idea, justice cannot exist independently of laws in order to be an acceptable criterion for judging and governing them. Hume considers the root and main motive of justice to be attention to individual interests (Self-interest). He emphasizes that self-interest is the main motive for establishing and stabilizing justice, which is accompanied by a kind of sympathy for public interests. This feeling of empathy causes the moral approval of this virtue (justice). (Ibid, 499-500) Hume's meaning is that pure individual self-interest cannot be the root of justice, because the act of developing laws is a collective action, so it must somehow include the mutual interests of individuals - not a particular individual. Therefore, the moment of the

establishment of justice and the establishment of laws is the moment when the individual interest in employment is considered with acceptance and empathy towards the interest of others. This empathy gives a value and moral dimension to the process of making laws and the commitment to comply with them - justice. Paying attention to the benefit of individual human beings encourages and motivates to have the laws of justice. In the natural state where there is a lack of laws, people see their property in danger and destruction and usurpation, hence, they feel the necessity of laws to protect their property from the encroachment of others. For an unknown reason, Hume makes the laws and principles of justice unique to the category of property, and he believes that the laws of justice and what people enact and formulate them in a natural state fall into three categories, all of which revolve around property. The first main category of justice laws is related to the establishment of the institution of ownership and its stabilization and respect. The second category is about the category of property transfer; That is, the legal and legitimate methods of transferring assets and property to others. And the third category is related to contracts and covenants concluded between people about their property and assets. Hume calls all these three main categories of laws justice.

Individual self-interest provides the necessary motivation to act to establish the laws of justice. Of course, in an atmosphere where the general conclusion is that these laws are in the interest of the general public; That is, the empathy that we mentioned before happens, but individual self-interest cannot be considered as the main motivation to be just, that is, to adhere to these rules, because perhaps in cases of personal interest, a person is at risk of breaking and disregarding these rules. And considering that no other internal motivation, such as love for the same kind, motivates obedience and respect for the laws, a valid executive guarantee such as punishments and fines should be considered so that people obey the laws because of the fear of them. After the answer Hume's summary comes to the question of the root and the main motivation behind the desire for justice, it is the turn to answer the second question, that is, the nature of the virtue of justice. As we will see, he interprets and analyzes the virtue of justice in such a way that it is in perfect proportion with his basis about the root of justice and its relationship with human laws.

Justice as an artificial virtue

The initial confrontation with Hume's words, especially his emphasis that no internal motivation invites us to justice and respect for the property of others and not to deprive them of their property, and it is only in the context of making laws that the question of justice and injustice - in the sense of commitment and non-commitment to Laws-subject, it raises the suspicion that Hume basically does not consider justice as a virtue. But a deeper reflection on

his words indicates that he does not consider justice to be a "natural virtue". He believes that justice is an "artificial" virtue. Justice is a virtue, because according to Hume, virtue and vice are matters that are the subject of moral judgment, and considering that justice and injustice are judged by human beings, justice is a virtue, although it is not a natural virtue.

The word natural is sometimes used in contrast to rare and rare, and this use of the word natural is not the place of discussion. Natural is sometimes used in contrast to artificial, which is exactly what he means by the unnaturalness of the virtue of justice. There is an inner urge and desire in a person to perform certain actions, therefore, a person sees himself as obligated to perform them. This internal and natural motivation and desire forces him to perform such acts. And if a person has this internal and natural tendency towards deficiency, he tries to compensate for it with a sense of duty. Due to the fact that there is no such internal desire and tendency in the existence of people to not take possession of other people's property and property, and there is no natural and inherent motivation to respect other people's property, laws should be enacted to force people to respect other people's property. . Due to the fact that these laws of justice are imposed by human hands and there is no internal motivation behind them, justice becomes artificial and fake.

The very important point is that Hume deduces the virtue of having justice (laws of ownership and respect and commitment to them) from its usefulness. According to Hume, all kinds of virtues (virtues), whether they are natural or artificial like justice, are of the nature of utility. Justice and its laws, according to Hume's analysis, are man-made and made by his hands, but its usefulness is not a fictitious and contractual matter, so the laws that have the character of usefulness and are agreed upon by people are considered virtues, and therefore, being a virtue Justice is not assigned to a specific place, time, and society. The laws of justice and its content, although they are associated with differences in terms of examples in different societies, because different societies and legal systems propose different sets of laws, but virtue is the principle of its place. There is no doubt, because the feature of usefulness accompanies them. The essence of these laws - whatever they are - is virtue, and the desire to obey them is also virtue (beneficial). Hume means that justice is artificial. But the feeling of being moral (virtue) is natural and non-artificial, that's exactly the point.

Hume mentions some differences between natural and artificial virtues, including the fact that the positive and good results arising from natural virtues can be attributed to each partial case as well. In the sense that each partial act of this type of virtues has a positive effect and result. will pursue, unlike justice, which will pursue the public interest when all are committed to the laws of justice, and the commitment of a particular person, if it is not accompanied by the obedience of others, will have no effect. Hume compares natural virtue like benevolence to a

wall and artificial virtue like justice to a vault. The charity and benevolent action of each person has the status of one brick, which contributes to raising the height of the wall according to its own size, even if others do not put the next bricks on it, but an arch is formed when all its components are provided together continuously, and then righteous actions A part of people and their obedience to the laws, if it is not accompanied by the commitment of others, will not lead to positive and good results.

From Hume's point of view, not only the subject of justice, but also concepts such as duty and obligation are subject to the existence of artificial human laws, and without the existence of these man-made laws, nothing called duty and obligation would have any meaning. It seems that tying these categories to man-made laws establishes a certain approach and theory about ethics. But can all moral concepts and predicates be considered artificial and dependent on the existence of human-made laws and conventions? Some commentators of Hume, such as Harrison, believe that in Hume's analysis of moral themes and virtues, a distinction should be made between two categories of moral concepts and predicates, and The first, which we call value words, includes concepts such as "good", "bad", "virtue" and "vice". On the other hand, in the realm of ethics, we are facing another group of concepts that lack the element of valuing actions and behavior. Concepts such as "right", "wrong", "permissible", "unauthorized" belong to this second category, which only express what should be done or can be done or should not be realized. Hume's emphasis on the dependence of moral concepts on man-made contracts and laws is aimed at the second category of moral concepts. But concepts

Such as kindness and benevolence and hard work can be considered virtues, even in a container where there are no artificial laws, because in such a situation (natural situation) they have the characteristic of being useful or agreed upon.

According to this interpretation, justice and supreme ethical titles and concepts become artificial and conventional, because they are tied to the subject laws, and this analysis can be considered a special theory about ethics.

The connection of justice with human-made contracts and laws does not mean that these contracts create a desire for justice in human beings. From Hume's point of view, if there are no contracts, there will be no motivation to do justice, but contracts and laws do not motivate, but rather they direct the existing motivations - especially the motivation of self-interest. interest) leads a person to take possession of other people's property and assets, but after the establishment of property laws, which considers the assignment of some property to each person as his legal right and recognizes the violation of the property of individuals as a cause

of punishment, the interest of individuals towards respecting the laws Justice leads. Of course, his current motivation to obey the laws of property and perform a just act is a combination of the fear of punishment and the fear of being deprived of the benefits that the implementation of these laws and their rule in the society will bring to him. Justice, as an artificial virtue, has a deep connection with the issue of ownership. Hume is of the opinion that the best view of justice is to see justice as the protector and guardian of the existing and ongoing structure of ownership; that is, the principles and laws of justice must serve to maintain the existing status of ownership and property transfer, and therefore, against insufficient and impossible The practicality of any other notion of justice that wants to disrupt the existing order and structure of ownership argues.

Hume believes that basically three models are envisioned for the problem of distribution of assets and property. Fair distribution of assets and property based on merit and entitlement (desert), distribution based on equality and the third model, which is the same as the current state of ownership and distribution of assets. His emphasis is on the fact that it is not possible to base justice and the rules governing the distribution of assets and ownership on merit and equality, and this current situation should be the basis of a fair structure of ownership. His argument is based on rejecting the element of merit and entitlement as the basis of ownership, that the criterion of merit is morally controversial, therefore, it cannot be the basis of general laws. In other words, people cannot agree on the general rules of ownership and define fair distribution based on these rules due to the lack of shared opinion about the meaning and examples of deservingness and entitlement. In the same way, relying on equality as a basis for property distribution is also unscientific, because in reality, people in society are not in an equal situation in terms of individual abilities and talents, so there is always a serious tendency towards inequality, which is only in the shadow of an authoritarian government. It can be controlled to some extent. Therefore, the equal distribution of opportunities and blessings requires the existence of an authoritarian and powerful political system, and this is a paradox, because it fuels political inequality. Hume comes to the conclusion that in order to preserve those assets and properties that people have (based on this current and natural order), laws must be established and any other attempt to change the structure of the fair distribution of assets and property is unsuccessful.

The conditions of justice

Undoubtedly, justice is a virtue, whether we consider it a natural virtue or evaluate it as an artificial virtue. The question is whether justice is an absolute virtue or one that is conditioned and bound by the existence of special conditions. What is meant by absolute virtue is that its value and validity are not conditioned by the existence of special conditions and it is

desirable and valid in all circumstances and situations. For example, in the world of theories and sciences, truth is an absolute criterion and value, because the truth and validity of every theorem and theory depends on having the truth. Therefore, the validity of the truth itself is not subject to special conditions, and the truth is unexceptionably and absolutely valid. From Hume's point of view, does justice have an absolute value like truth?

Hume's emphasis on the remedial and restorative character of having the virtue of justice (Remedial Virtue) prevents him from believing in the absolute validity of justice, because from his point of view, justice and its laws become necessary when there are certain conditions in which the laws of justice and It is a treatment of the event and helps to repair the situation. In the situation and conditions where the scope of conflicts and disagreements reaches such an extent that moral and political considerations cannot end them, it is the turn of the laws of justice to become the basis of conflict resolution. In such a situation, justice becomes the superior virtue over other virtues, just like the virtue of bravery on the battlefield. It is not the case that universal courage is a superior virtue in every situation, even outside of the battlefield. In order to make the conditional nature of the virtue of justice more clear, I would like to draw your attention to the fact that, according to Hume, sometimes justice is not essentially a virtue; For example, in a situation where the atmosphere of pure benevolence and charity prevails over the people of a society, the discussion of justice and the laws of justice is basically pointless and it is unnecessary and even anti-value. For example, in an ideal and intimate family where the spirit of honesty and complete intimacy is established among people, although sometimes there is a conflict of interests, they rarely resort to the issue of rights. This is not because of the spread of injustice and usurpation, but the adherence to the laws of justice and the realization of legal rights has been overshadowed by sincerity and goodwill, because in such an atmosphere and conditions, the amount of share that each person takes from the benefits and property of the family is basically the cause of concern for people. It won't happen anymore. Of course, if the family conditions change and due to the intensity of the family conflict, the realization of individual rights requires the laws and principles of justice, then justice is considered a virtue. In any case, the conditions that make justice a virtue are flexible and variable, and the conditions are possible. It should be changed in such a way that the plan of justice not only has no virtue, but turns into a vice; For example, in a family that lives in a friendly and completely monotonous atmosphere, if one of the family members has a problem and a costly illness, and other people are willing to help him with full satisfaction and compassion, the issue of the rights and interests of each person and the necessity Dividing the family based on the laws of justice is unnecessary and even causes people's resentment.

It is very natural that Hume, with his own interpretation of justice and considering it artificial, and limiting the function of justice to solving property disputes and dividing property and assets, reaches such a conclusion and considers justice a conditional and non-absolute virtue. He says:

The emergence of justice is rooted in human conventions... and these conventions are intended to remedy some conflicts that are caused by the symmetry of the special characteristics of the human soul with the position of external objects. Selfishness and limited generosity are among the special characteristics. It is human's sensuality, and the position of external objects refers to things such as the ease of their change, their rarity compared to human desires and desires... With a proportional increase in the benevolence of humans or the generosity of nature and the replacement of nobler virtues and the existence of more blessings, justice is replaced by It becomes unnecessary and useless.

Hume mentions a number of conditions that, according to his belief, the existence of these conditions makes justice useful and, as a result, attribute justice and its laws to virtue. In the absence of one of these conditions, justice is no longer considered a virtue, because it loses the basis of virtue, that is, usefulness. Here I mention some of these conditions in passing.

The first condition is what Hume calls "moderate scarcity". If something is not basically rare; That is, if it is found in abundance and satisfies human demand and desire completely and easily, like the air that breathes, there is no need to divide it fairly and justice in such cases is useless and pointless. On the other hand, if the scarcity of a thing is not moderate, but extremely scarce and rare, then talking about fair distribution based on the laws of justice is invalid and useless, because it cannot be distributed among people due to the extreme scarcity. The issue of justice is things that have a moderate scarcity. Another condition of justice is "moderate selfishness". Naturally, there is an element of selfishness in humans, but extreme and unbridled selfishness cannot be considered as inherent and natural to human beings, what hinders the issue of justice is extreme selfishness, otherwise general selfishness, which exists more in nature, is an obstacle to the issue of justice. is not. Extreme selfishness does not consider a fair share for others in order to divide and distribute property, interests and assets based on fair principles and rules. On the other hand, extreme benevolence and charity (lack of selfishness) also hinders the usefulness of justice, because as we have mentioned in the past, if there is unconventional generosity and charity among the people of a society, the laws of justice lose their usefulness. Therefore, moderate selfishness, which is the boundary between extreme selfishness and total benevolence, is a necessary condition for the virtue of justice. (Hume: 1888, 492-497) Among the other conditions of justice is the existence of proportionality in the amount of power of people in society. If in a society some

people have very unequal power, justice becomes practically useless, because nothing can oblige them to comply with the laws of justice and obey its requirements. There is no need to assume an example here. Hume mentions an example of the relationship between the civilized Europeans and the natives of India and shows how the superior power of the immigrant Europeans compared to the natives of India led them to behave arrogantly, in such a way that they treated the Indians like animals with a contemptuous look at them. They did not only violate the principles of justice, but also human principles with this arrogant behavior. (Hume: 1975, 197)

The topic of the conditions of justice has been the focus of some thinkers after Hume; For example, John Rawls defines the conditions of justice as the natural conditions under which the conditions of human cooperation - in order to outline the principles of justice - become both possible and necessary, and he considers this view of the conditions of justice to be borrowed by Hume. (Rawls: 109) Although Rawls, like Hume, considers the principles and rules of justice to be artificial and created and a kind of human agreement and agreement, not eternal truths that can be discovered and understood by the power of understanding or conscience and human conscience, and both depend on this agreement and agreements. Specific conditions speak, but Rawls's view of the conditions of justice and the function of these conditions is different from Hume's view of the conditions of justice. According to Hume, the function of the conditions of justice is what justifies the need for the laws of justice and provides reasons for its usefulness. Secondly, it grounds the necessary motivation to set up and falsify the laws and principles of justice, while according to Rawls, the conditions of justice refer to the things that the fairness of the agreement has been done, in the original position (original position) with respect to It guarantees the principles of justice. According to Rawls, the conditions of justice, in fact, express the situation that surrounds people in the first situation. Things like neglecting one's personal interests and position, this situation causes people to agree on the principles of justice in a way and conditions that cannot interfere with their individual interests, and this guarantees the fairness of the content of the contracts and agreements made about the principles of justice. The conditions of Hume's justice are completely different from the conditions mentioned by Kant to understand the principles of justice. Hume draws the conditions of justice according to the internal realities of man, especially his desires and instincts such as his utilitarianism on the one hand and the external realities and objective limitations of human society on the other hand, and tries to enumerate these conditions with an empiricist view. In drawing these conditions, Rasahim does not focus on moral and ethical issues, metaphysical and rational dos and don'ts. Just on the opposite point, according to Kant, the conditions of justice are formed in an ideal space and a special realm, which is far from the experimental and normal and natural life of a

person. From Kant's point of view, when a person reaches the understanding of moral principles and principles of justice, when he ignores his personal interests and goals and sees himself in the realm of ends and does not look at others as a means, in such a situation he finds good will and laws and The principles that he understands in this situation are the requirements of pure reason, hence, the principles of justice and morality are absolute matters, and as a result, they are necessary and unexceptionable.

Evaluation and criticism of Hume's theory of justice

It was observed that Hume, influenced by Hobbes, in his famous book *Leviathan*, inspired by the idea of the "state of nature", depicted an idea of justice that has the role of treating and repairing the conflicts and differences of the natural state - in the absence of law and order. Therefore, justice is the description of a system and a set of laws, especially the laws that are forged and enacted to regulate matters related to ownership, assets, and interests. Considering that Hume believes that the basis and source of the value and virtue of justice is the common good and its usefulness, and he believes that adherence to these laws satisfies the moderate selfishness and utilitarianism of individuals, and this feeling is the necessary motivation for individuals to leave the provides the natural state and giving in to the state of property laws, his theory of justice is classified under the theory of justice that believes in "Utilitarianism". The existence of expressions such as "Public Utility" or "Public Interest" (Public interest) in Hume's words and his emphasis that observing and establishing the laws of justice is in the interest of the public, although it brings him closer to the defenders of utilitarianism and his theory of justice instead of assigning it to models such as "Mutual Advantage" and "Intuitionism" (Intuitionism) attributes to the Utilitarianism model. But in the interpretation of Hume's utilitarianism, we should not fall into the error of anachronism and attribute Bentham's and James Mill's interpretation of utilitarianism, which are later than Hume's in terms of time. (Barry: 1989, 168) The famous and common utilitarianism, which owes to the thought of Bentham and Mill, is based on the idea that in the final analysis there is only one fundamental value and virtue, and that is maximizing collective benefit (Utility Maximizing) and this value It should be the basis of all social institutions and political-economic decisions. If we consider utilitarianism as a theory of justice, the emphasis of this theory will be that social justice is achieved in the shadow of providing and paying attention to this basic value. According to this criterion, it may be considered utilitarianism to violate some basic and general notions of justice - about two people who have equal rights and responsibilities - if this neglect and ignoring of rights ultimately leads to the maximization of collective benefit. The term utilitarianism is based on the belief that the good of different people It is tied together and the collective good that results from the good of individuals can also be an indicator of the benefit of individuals. Therefore, maximizing the benefit of the society

ultimately indicates the promotion of the benefit of the members of the society, then this maximization of the collective benefit should be at the forefront of the society's goals in legislation, implementation and macro decisions.

It is clear that Hume does not consider such a role for the collective good, and his advice is not to base the collective good and maximize it for the majority of people for the category of developing the laws of justice. Hume does not recommend that the principles and laws of justice should be set based on the benefit of the majority of people and to maximize it, rather he says that the motivation of people in a natural state to change this situation and turn to the laws of justice is their individual benefit, and if these laws are followed They also pursue the public interest. This attention to the public interest also gives the laws of justice a moral foundation and value (virtue), because according to Hume's theory of ethics, something of value and moral virtue is considered useful.

From another point of view, Hume's theory of justice is a type of conventionalism, because it makes justice dependent on a set of subjective laws and defines fair action as respect and commitment to these laws and contracts. Of course, contractualism has various forms; For example, the famous definition of justice - granting the rights of every right holder - can be contractualist, if we accept that the rights of individuals are determined by institutions, legal contracts and sets of relevant laws. But if we consider the rights of individuals not based on human-made laws and contracts, but as arising from the system of nature and divine laws, and if we consider human rights as natural rights that are not established or resolved by human hands or human agreements, then this famous definition will not indicate contractualism. Was. In any case, Hume clearly defends contractualism by linking rights and justice to artificial human contracts and laws. We begin the criticism of Hume's theory of justice with his specific criticism of human beings. His theory of justice is obviously based on a highly empiricist view of human beings, and in this narrow view, the place of reason and human moral perceptions has been obviously ignored. Raymond Plant rightly seeks the secret of why Hume does not present a rich and comprehensive conception of man in his adherence to explicit and absolute empiricism. This strict empiricism has practically deprived Hume of the possibility of presenting any rich and complete epistemological theory about man. Based on Hume's empiricism and epistemological foundations, there is basically no fixed and unchangeable thing called "Self" to be the subject of empirical research. Hume, relying on sensory perception, only acknowledges the existence of things that affect our emotional and experimental powers, and our sensory perception powers never recognize the fixed and unchangeable thing called Person or Self in an experimental process. They do not place

themselves. There is no specific experience or sensory perception that provides a fixed concept and idea of a person or person, so when it comes to human cognition, we are faced with scattered, different and variable sensory perceptions, and there is no fixed and unchangeable sensory cognition that It represents a human being. We feel fear, love, cold and heat, hunger and thirst in our existence, but we never perceive something called "Myself" independently of these scattered and changing experiential and sensory perceptions in order to theorize about its essence. Therefore, whenever we talk about a human being or an individual, instead of referring to a clear idea of a human being and ourselves, we refer to a set of these experimental and sensory perceptions and perceptions. This epistemological view fundamentally denies an empirical and fixed reality called human being as a fixed truth that should be the center and subject of anthropology, because experience and sensory perception cannot prove the existence of this common constant among human beings. Denial of empiricism Extremism and investigating the epistemological position of human reason is one of the important topics of epistemology that requires a wide area, which is far from the purpose of this article. Also, Hume's moral basis and denial of necessary moral knowledge and linking virtues and values to utility and providing an empirical interpretation of utility are all very important controversial issues that moral philosophy is responsible for.

It means that the philosophical foundations of Hume's theory of justice in many cases in the relevant fields such as anthropology, epistemology and moral philosophy are faced with serious challenges and criticisms, and the credibility of his theory of justice depends on overcoming these challenges. We have mentioned the issues - the failure to infer should from is - also affects Hume's theory of justice, and it itself suffers from the fallacy of should and is. On the one hand, Hume links justice with compliance with existing laws about property and emphasizes that if these laws are not respected, people will be immersed in a state of nature and chaos caused by the lack of law and justice. Therefore, he infers the value and virtue of having justice and its laws from a reality called usefulness and the effect of adherence to laws on the elimination of chaos, i.e. "must" and the proposition of value from the reality of "is" - usefulness - outside kills, and this is the same thing that Hume invites everyone to avoid in his philosophy. Hume describes justice as property laws and believes that in the absence of law, neither justice nor injustice has any issue. With the emergence of the law, something called the rights of individuals and justice will become meaningful, and justice and fair action will consist of compliance and commitment to these laws. It seems that Hume neglected a very important point, and that is that the question of justice, Hume's epistemology, which is based on pure empiricism, leads to many unconventional results and doubts the truth of many philosophical and rational concepts and propositions; For example, he denies causality and cause-and-effect relationship, because according to his epistemological basis, our sense and

experience of watching the impact of the hand on the ball and the movement of the ball after this impact is only capable of understanding the sequence of the movement of the ball following the movement of the hand. , but our senses do not perceive something called cause and causal connection. Therefore, the law of causation and the necessity of the realization of the effect cannot be verified after the realization of the cause, because the sense and experience do not confirm it. The question precedes the law, because the law itself is a matter of justice and injustice. Just as an external action can be an example of just or unjust action, the law can be just or unjust. Therefore, the question of whether this law is fair or unfair, fair or cruel, appropriate or inappropriate, is naturally raised in the case of any contract, agreement and law. If justice is a description of the law and means compliance with the law and not a higher criterion for measuring the validity and validity of the law, then any law in any form and with any content should be described as being just, even though this is against reality and common sense. Man-made laws, which are the result of the agreement of a few or the majority, do not by themselves guarantee fairness - that too in all possible cases.

Another weakness of Hume's theory of justice is due to the exclusiveness of the laws of justice to the category of property and the three issues related to it. As some critics and commentators of Hume state, Hume's extreme emphasis on linking the issue of justice with property is misleading, and basically the psychological and historical reasons for such emphasis are unclear. Humans have many needs, one of which is the need for property and possessions, and on the other hand, it is completely logically wrong to think that all human conflicts and disputes are rooted in the ownership of rare things. (Harrison: 1981, 42) Law and order is not only for regulating property affairs and curbing financial disputes, but collective life has various dimensions that the laws of justice are necessary to regulate all types of these relationships.

Hume's theory of justice is silent about the way of distribution of favors and blessings, such as wealth and natural resources, social status and positions, as well as labors and hardships and tasks of social life. The key to this silence is that, according to Hume's approach, any legal system and set of rules with any legal content is called justice, despite this, the general approval leaves no room for selecting specific criteria or a specific legal system as the optimal and ideal system for the distribution of primary benefits. . Hume's perception of justice practically blocks the path of comparative and critical discussion in the field of proposed models about the desirable and fair social structure. Another point is that in Hume's theory of justice, the question of why we should adhere to the laws of justice does not find a clear answer. Let's remember that Hume denied the existence of a natural and internal desire

and motivation to do justice, and he abstracted the virtue of justice from its usefulness, and considered the main motive behind the act of forging and compiling justice laws to be selfishness and human selfishness. This analysis may cover the cases where following the laws of specific individual interest is followed and justify the necessity of adhering to the laws of justice - regardless of the fallacy it should and is - but there are many cases where the individual interest of a person in breaking the law and It is disregarding it. In these cases, what argumentative basis will justify the necessity of paying attention to the individual and his practical commitment to the laws of justice? Hume's theoretical, ethical, and anthropological assumptions block the way to finding a proper answer to this question.

Result

From the investigations carried out in this article, it can be concluded that the argument of order as a philosophical argument is not a successful argument. In addition, the interpretation based on parables has serious problems. In this article, it was shown that the answer to Hume's harsh criticisms is not an easy task and Professor Motahari's answers to Hume's criticisms do not seem to be successful. It was also shown that although Professor Motahari tried to reject Hume's criticisms on the reason of order in some of his works and considered it as a non-empirical reason, but in some of his other works, he implied many of Hume's evaluations towards He has approved the reason for order and is very close to his point of view. Just as Hume believed that reasoning through order cannot be considered as a successful argument in philosophical terms because it is not able to prove the God desired by religious people in different religious traditions, because it is only a part of the elements of theism. confirms and is completely ambiguous compared to other parts; In the end, Professor Motahari considered the argument of order to be irrational, because it lacks the conditions of a philosophical argument; And for this reason, it is believed that such proofs alone cannot prove the desired God of religious people. And it has been clarified that the reason of order cannot prove the necessity, antiquity, unity, infinity of God and His omniscience and power. He has stated that the reason of order or the reason of guidance is enough to make us understand that nature is subject to a supernatural force, and this amount will not be enough to know God, and therefore, like Hume, he considers the reason of order to be of limited use.

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